

Interoperable applications suite to enhance European identity and document Security and fraud detection

EINSTEIN

Horizon Europe – 101121280

D2.1 ELSI Impact Assessment

Deliverable nature:	OTHER
Dissemination level: (Confidentiality)	Public (PU)
Version:	1.0
Date:	31-07-2024
Keywords:	architecture, biometrics, interfaces, components, border management, European Union.

The EINSTEIN project is funded by the European Union (EU) under G.A. no. 101121280 and UKRI Funding Service under IFS reference 10093453. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect the views of the EU/Executive Agency or UKRI. Neither the EU nor the granting authority nor UKRI can be held responsible for them.

Executive summary

The report is developed in the scope of WP2 – Requirements (ethical and technical) and Applications’ Specification. The report provides a detailed documentation of the first execution of the Ethical, Legal, Societal Impact Assessment of the EINSTEIN Applications in the identity management ecosystem. It serves as a guide to the design and development work of the EINSTEIN consortium, ensuring the solutions developed within the protect and promote fundamental rights.

The Impact Assessment is underpinned by an integrated methodology for ethical, legal and societal issues (ELSI). This first iteration of the assessment focuses on outlining the key legal frameworks and standards underpinning the protection of fundamental rights, in addition to providing an overview of the European legislative and policy ecosystem for digital identity management. This is followed by an assessment of the EINSTEIN solutions at two levels:

- Component level, addressing the impacts of biometric technologies, artificial intelligence, and self-service technologies.
- Applications, addressing the impacts of each of the 6 EINSTEIN applications.

Recommendations for mitigating/preventative actions are provided for ELSI risks, as are recommendations for enhancing/enabling actions for ELSI opportunities. The expected use cases for the EINSTEIN Applications address both border management and law enforcement. These domains have the potential for serious and far-reaching impacts, both positive and negative, and, as such, the integration of any new capability must be carefully assessed. This initial assessment reflects the current status of Application development and will be reviewed and updated as the project progresses, taking into account field-level developments across the lifecycle of the project.

The integration of the ELSI recommendations into the technical design and development will be monitored across the development and testing cycles of the Applications. These recommendations will be complemented by guidance provided by the EINSTEIN Ethical Advisory Board (EAB). Central to this process will be managing the complexities of conflicting/contradictory values underpinning the design process. These issues will be investigated under T2.3, where the ELSI recommendations developed within the IA will be translated into formal requirements.

Document Information

Project Number	Horizon Europe - 101121280	Acronym	EINSTEIN
Full Title	Interoperable applications suite to enhance European identity and document Security and fraud detection		
Project URL	http://www.einstein-horizon.eu		
Document URL			
EU Project Officer	Bruno Chenard		

Date of Delivery	Contractual	M7	Actual	MX
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Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev. No.	Author	Change
19-03-2024	0.0	Eileen Murphy	Initial Revision
23-05-2024	0.1	Christine Andreeva Eileen Murphy	Rework of sections
19-06-2024	0.2	Christine Andreeva Eileen Murphy	Further drafting
01-07-2024	0.3	Christine Andreeva Eileen Murphy	Sent for WP lead/T2.1 partner review
03-07-2024	0.4	Christine Andreeva Eileen Murphy	Sent for internal Trilateral Review
12-07-2024	0.5	Christine Andreeva Eileen Murphy	Sent for consortium review Sent for EAB review
26-07-2024	0.6	Eileen Murphy	Revision
31-07-2024	1.0	Georgios Stavropoulos	Final checks, language review

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Explanation
ABC	Automated Border Control
AFIS	Automated Fingerprint Identification System
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIA	AI Act
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy AI for self-assessment
API	Advanced Passenger Information
Art. X	Article X
BAC	Basic Access Control
BAS	Biometric Assessment Service
BCP	Border Crossing Point
BSI	the Federal Cyber Security Authority of Germany
CE-VIS	Central Element – Visa Information System
CFR	Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU
CIR	Common Identity Repository
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
CSCA	Country Signing Certification Authority
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
DoA	Description of Action
DPA	Data Protection Act
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DSC	Document Signer Certificate
DTC	Digital Travel Credential
DTC-PC	Digital Travel Credential – Physical Component
DTC-VC	Digital Travel Credential – Virtual Component
DX.X	Deliverable X.X
EAB	Ethics Advisory Board
EAC	Extended Access Control
EBSI	European Blockchain Services Infrastructure
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
ECTHR	European Court of Human Rights
EES	Entry Exit System
eIDAS	electronic Identification, Authentication and trust services
ELSI	Ethical, Legal, Societal Issues
eMRTD	Electronic Machine Readable Travel Document
EPRIS	European Police Records Index System
ESC	European Social Charter
ESP	European Search Portal
ETIAS	European Travel Information and Authorisation Systems
EU	European Union
EUDI	European Digital Identity
Eurodac	European Asylum Dactyloscopy Database
FAR	False Acceptance Rate
FIQA	Face Image Quality Assessment
FRR	False Rejection Rate
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GDPR EUI	General Data Protection Regulation European Union Institutions

HIC	Human In Command
HITL	Human In The Loop
HOTL	Human On The Loop
IA	Impact Assessment
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organisation
JHA	Justice and Home Affairs
LDS2	Logical Data Structure 2
LEAs	Law Enforcement Authorities
LED	Law Enforcement Directive
MAD	Morphing Attack Detection
MID	Multiple-Identity Detector
MoSCoW	Must have; Should have; Could have; Won't have
MRTD	Machine Readable Travel Document
MS	Member State
NFC	Near Field Communication
N-VIS	National – Visa Information System
OFIQ	Open Source Facial Image Quality
PAD	Presentation Attack Detection
PET	Privacy Enhancing Technology
PIUs	Passenger Information Units
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
PNR	Passenger Name Records
RBI	Remote Biometric Identification
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SAC	Supplemental Access Control
sBMS	shared Biometric Matching Service
SIS-II	Schengen Information System II
SLTD	Stolen Lost Travel Document
SPOC	Single Point of Contact
SST	Self-Service Technology
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identity
TCN	Third Country National
TEU	Treaty on the European Union
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
TX.X	Task X.X.
UI	User Interface
uID	Unique ID
UX	User Experience
VIS	Visa Information System
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

Deliverable (D2.1) covers the results of the work performed within Task T2.1 “Ethical, legal, and societal issues (ELSI) monitoring and impact assessment” during M1-M6 of the project. According to the EINSTEIN Description of Action (DoA), the presented deliverable will address ELSI in identity management, focusing on an Impact Assessment (IA) of the EINSTEIN technologies ecosystem. The EINSTEIN project will develop 6 Applications addressing identity and document fraud:

- Online id issuance,
- Mobile document and identity check,
- Document authentication,
- Pre-registration for border crossing,
- EES kiosk with advanced fraud detection,
- Fast track for enrolled travellers.

Each of the Applications will incorporate biometric technologies (for either identity verification or authentication) and algorithms to aid morphing attack detection (MAD) and/or presentation attack detection (PAD). In addition, several of the Applications will be self-service technologies (SST). The Applications will be applied in both border management and law enforcement contexts. Developing the technical means and supporting infrastructure required to achieve digital identity management has been identified as a priority action within the EU.¹ This work must ensure the security of the identity check, aid the detection of potential fraud, while also preserving, even enhancing the rights and freedoms of individuals and society. The design and development of the Applications will seek to embed privacy and security enhancing technologies and techniques in a decentralised architecture, in addition to adhering to state-of-the-art EU guidance for AI systems. The IA aims to not only ensure the minimum levels of compliance, but seeks to develop meaningful engagement with stakeholders and collaboratively identify opportunities to fulfil and protect the fundamental rights and societal values related to identity management.

The main purpose of the document is to present and describe in detail the IA methodology to be applied during the lifecycle of the project; the steps taken to engage and support project partners for ELSI compliance in the design and development of the EINSTEIN solutions; and the results of the first round of IA applied to the EINSTEIN solutions based on their current status of development. The results of the IA will guide the design and development process of the EINSTEIN solutions to ensure they are compliant with the highest ethical, legal, and societal standards and expectations.

Chapter 2 presents the IA methodology and the framework of engagement developed to engage partners and end-users on ELSI. The IA will be applied iteratively across the lifecycle of the project in parallel to the testing cycle of the solutions. Findings from the IA will be translated into functional and non-functional requirements (T2.3). Incorporation of ELSI requirements will be traced using a requirements traceability matrix and aligned with the methodology for technical requirements being executed under T2.4.

Chapter 3 describes key frameworks governing ELSI and identity management. This includes relevant frameworks for fundamental rights, a review of both the GDPR and LED as they relate to the processing of personal data, a review of the AI Act and the guidance provided herein. In addition, a high-level overview of the policy landscape for identity management is provided, including legislative developments on border checks, large-scale IT systems and interoperability, and ongoing work on the implementation of Digital Travel Credentials (DTC) and Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI). This work will be updated across future iterations of the IA, tracking relevant legislative developments that will impact the proposed EINSTEIN solutions and their future deployment.

Chapter 4 describes the results of the first IA. The focus of this analysis is on the component level, providing guidance to consortium partners on potential ELSI risks for biometric technologies, AI and algorithms and self-

¹ European Commission, 2021.

service technologies (SST). A second level of analysis – Application – identifies related ELSI for the EINSTEIN Applications. This level of analysis will be further developed in the next iteration of the IA, as the EINSTEIN solutions mature along the testing cycle.

Next steps for T2.1 are described in Chapter 5, with a focus on communicating/monitoring compliance with the results of the first IA and identifying actions for the next iteration. To maintain the readability of the report, supporting materials have been made available as Annexes.

2 ELSI Impact Assessment Methodology

Previous research has demonstrated the importance of carrying out assessments as part of new technology developments to better understand the potential impacts of deployment.² Overtime, individual methods have developed targeting specific areas of impact (e.g. legal, ethical, privacy/data protection, socio-economic, etc.). Many of these methods address issues with cross-cutting impacts. Thus, the EINSTEIN project will apply an integrated ethical, legal and societal issues (ELSI) impact assessment methodology.

An impact assessment (IA) is a framework for ensuring ELSI are "... adequately examined by stakeholders before deployment and so that mitigation measures can be taken as necessary".³ The IA process involves analysing, monitoring, and managing intended and unintended consequences, both positive and negative. An integrated impact assessment focuses on various types of potential consequences of proposed actions, such as ELSI. A key outcome of an IA is recommendations targeting the design and development stage, when there is still an opportunity to make adjustments to either mitigate/prevent potential ELSI risks and enable/enhance ELSI opportunities. IAs are a cornerstone of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). The IA should be conducted in collaboration with both project partners and other relevant stakeholders to identify, discuss, and find ways of dealing with ELSI.⁴ An IA should not only identify potential risks but should also weigh these risks against the potential benefits the technology will provide. Understanding the trade-offs between risks and benefits is a complex process, particularly in the field of border management and law enforcement where the consequences of novel solution development and deployment are both serious and far reaching.

Wright and Friedewald⁵ map the key steps of an integrated privacy and ethics impact assessment process:

- Prepare
- Analyse
- Report and act.

These steps provide the foundation for the IA methodology, and have been adapted to the requirements of the EINSTEIN project. The goal of the current IA is to identify the main risks associated with the component technologies that will be integrated into the EINSTEIN Applications. As the component technologies will be combined in different ways, for different use cases, across both border management and law enforcement the assessment takes a broad approach to the identification of risks. These risks will then be prioritised and tailored to the goals of the EINSTEIN Applications through further engagement with consortium partners and external stakeholders.⁶ As the EINSTEIN Applications are in various stages of development, it should be noted that not all the required information to complete all steps is currently available. This information will be captured in future iterations of the IA. The following section outlines how the IA methodology has been operationalised for the EINSTEIN project.

2.1 Application to EINSTEIN

2.1.1 Prepare

The need for an IA has already been established and incorporated into the EINSTEIN project structure. The IA team consists primarily of T2.1 project partners (TRI, CERTH, IDM, UREAD, VD). TRI will lead the task and oversee the IA development. Each of the contributing partners is a WP leader for the technical development, piloting, and exploitation of the EINSTEIN solutions.⁷ For each iteration of the IA, contributing partners will support the

² See for example, Wright, 2011.

³ Ibid, p. 223.

⁴ Ibid, p. 200.

⁵ Wright and Friedewald, 2013, p. 764.

⁶ This work will take place under WP2, T2.3, which will elaborate ethical, legal, and societal requirements for the EINSTEIN components and Applications.

⁷ TNO, as the WP5 leader, is not formally represented in the T2.1 description. However, they have been actively engaged in the process and have participated in the same activities as other WP leaders to ensure a balanced application of the IA.

implementation of ELSI recommendations and TRI will monitor for compliance with T2.1/WP2 outputs. The ELSI impact assessment runs the lifecycle of the EINSTEIN project and will be applied iteratively. The first assessment is presented in this report. The report draws on:

- Desk-based research to identify and summarise previous ELSI research on the development and deployment of border management and law enforcement identity management technologies, and
- Engaging with consortium partners on the technical design process to provide initial recommendations for the development of the EINSTEIN solutions.

Several elements of the EINSTEIN Applications have already undergone an IA as part of the previous projects outputs which EINSTEIN seeks to mature (i.e. D4FLY, iMARS, SMILE). This work will provide the baseline of the application of the ELSI IA in this first round, tailored to the objectives and workplans of EINSTEIN. Task 2.1 has also leveraged the inclusion of WP leads to build strong lines of communication between the ELSI IA of WP2 and the technical development of WP3-WP5, and the piloting and exploitation work of WP6 and WP7, respectively. This has involved completing a self-assessment form on how WPs are incorporating key ethical principles in their design work, and contributing an ELSI perspective to technical discussions through participation in WP3-WP5 calls.⁸

The ELSI assessment will be applied a further two times in line with the testing cycle of the EINSTEIN solutions. These results will be captured in the appropriate deliverables of WP2. The assessment will be applied at multiple levels including:

Table 1: Application of the IA

IA Level of Analysis	IA Iteration
Component level: addresses potential ELSI related to the key building blocks that compose the EINSTEIN Applications: biometric technologies, AI and algorithms, and self-service technologies.	1 st Iteration (D2.1) Updated across iterations as needed.
Application level: addresses potential ELSI that may arise during the integration of the above components into the proposed EINSTEIN Applications.	1 st Iteration (D2.1) 2 nd Iteration (D2.4)
Interoperability/eco-system level: addresses potential ELSI that may arise during the integration of the EINSTEIN Applications into their proposed operating environments.	2 nd Iteration (D2.4) 3 rd Iteration (D2.4)
Post-project exploitation level: addresses potential ELSI that may arise in relation to future uptake and adoption of the EINSTEIN Applications.	3 rd Iteration (D2.4)

The IA levels will guide the identification of potential ELSI risks and opportunities. Assessing for ELSI at different levels highlights the importance of context when carrying out ELSI IAs, and provides flexibility to keep pace with the development cycles of the Application. The IA process will be mapped against the timeline of solution testing, so it may provide recommendations in relation to each major stage of development, as visualised below.

⁸ As WP6 and WP7 are not yet active, these activities have targeted WP3-WP5. They will be extended to WP6 and WP7 as they open and captured in future iterations of the IA.

Figure 1: IA and solution testing⁹

The IA method incorporates a “by-design” approach, targeting its recommendations and interventions at the design and development activities of the EINSTEIN project. As EINSTEIN is an Innovation Action, the methodology places particular emphasis on understanding potential ELSI that might arise in the context of operationalisation. The application of the IA is addressed in Chapter 4, including a description of the solutions to be assessed at both component and Application level.

2.1.2 Analyse

The analysis step focuses on identifying and analysing potential impacts, consulting with stakeholders, checking for legislative compliance, and identifying potential risks/opportunities. The current iteration of the IA focuses on:

- Reviewing key legislative frameworks that will impact the development and deployment of the EINSTEIN solutions (Chapter 3).
- Consulting with partners leading the technical development of the solutions (T2.1 activities).¹⁰
- Outlining ELSI risks and opportunities and developing recommendations based on previous/ongoing research on identity management technologies (Chapter 4).

2.1.3 Report and act.

This step in the IA focuses on developing recommendations, publishing and implementing findings, external validation of the IA process, and updating the recommendations as required.

The findings of the first IA will be published in this report (D2.1), with subsequent iterations reported on in D2.4 (M34). The implementation of IA recommendations will be traced as part of translating the ELSI into design requirements, using a requirements traceability process (T2.3). The IA process will be externally validated by the EINSTEIN Ethical Advisory Board (EAB). Recommendations from the EAB will be similarly incorporated in the IA

⁹ The results of the EINSTEIN trials will be assessed under WP6, including ELSI metrics but will not undergo a 4th ELSI Impact Assessment.

¹⁰ The current IA has focused on engaging with consortium partners to understand the proposed technologies. Future iterations of the IA will continue to engage with these partners to capture the maturation of the solutions, but will also be expanded to include border management and law enforcement authorities as users/operators of each Application; the segments of the public interacting with the Applications; CSOs as representatives of wider society, with a particular focus on organisations representing the rights of vulnerable groups and populations (e.g. asylum seekers and refugees, differently abled, the young and the elderly) and policy makers. This work will build on the findings of D2.2, ‘Use Cases and User Needs Report’.

process and translated into requirements. The integration of WP2 across the EINSTEIN solution development process, supported by user training in WP6 will help to embed ELSI awareness across the project, with an emphasis on accountability.

Finally, it is worth noting that the focus of this IA is on understanding the potential impacts of the EINSTEIN solutions as they are intended for integration into the identity management ecosystem. While the recommendations focus on making interventions at the design and development stages of the project, they do not address the ethics of the research process itself, e.g. use of informed consent, recruitment of participants, etc. Rather, this work is addressed under WP1.

Chapters 3 and 4 will now present the results of the first IA.

3 Key Frameworks for ELSI

The analysis of ELSI relies on key legislative and professional frameworks that guide the application and uptake of the IA. These are summarised below and will make up the core reference materials used to support the IA.

3.1 Fundamental Rights

The development and deployment of systems for the use of border management and law enforcement must comply with the relevant human and fundamental rights laws and regulations to guarantee the civil rights and liberties enshrined therein. The European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR)¹¹ represents the main basis for human rights law and, together with the European Social Charter (ESC)¹², applies to EU Member States (MS) and the UK alike. The EU has its own legal instruments focusing on fundamental rights, namely the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU (CFR)¹³. Respect to human rights is also enshrined in the EU treaties: the Treaty on the European Union (TEU) and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU).¹⁴ The EU treaties are binding agreements between EU MS. Article 2 of the TEU establishes that "the Union is founded on the values of respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and respect for human rights, including the rights of persons belonging to minorities". These rights are outlined below.

The unalienable **right to life and prohibition of torture** must be guaranteed as enshrined in:

- Right to life (Art. 2 ECHR)
- Prohibition of torture and inhuman or degrading treatment (Art. 3)

To ensure **human dignity, physical and mental integrity**, specifically in the context of functions such as surveillance, data collection and prediction, border management and law enforcement systems must comply with the following legal bases:

- Human dignity (Art. 1, ECHR; Art. 1 CFR)
- Right to the Integrity of the person (Art. 3 CFR)
- Right to liberty and security (Art. 5 ECHR; Art 6 CFR)

To guarantee human **freedom and autonomy**, and comply with the right to freedom of expression and assembly, the following legal bases must be respected:

- Freedom of expression (Art. 10 ECHR; Art. 11 CFR)
- Freedom of assembly and association (Art. 11, ECHR; Art 12. CFR)
- Freedom of movement and of residence (Art. 45 CFR)

To provide for **non-discrimination and equality**, border management and law enforcement systems must strive to identify and remove discriminative data and biased algorithms, in order to ensure equal and symmetrical treatment of people from various ethnic, social, economic backgrounds, and from different nationalities. Furthermore, they must guarantee freedom of thought and religion, and the practices enshrined therein. The legal bases are to be found in:

- Prohibition of discrimination (Art. 14 ECHR; Art. 21 CFR; Art. 10 TFEU)
- Freedom of thought, conscience and religion (Art. 9 ECHR)

¹¹ Council of Europe, 1950.

¹² Council of Europe, 1961.

¹³ European Union, 2016. To access case law of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) and the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) for the different Articles of the EU CFR, please see: <https://fra.europa.eu/en/case-law-database>

¹⁴ European Union, 2012a and 2012b.

- Equality between men and women (Art. 23 CFR)
- As well as within the Employment Equality Directive (2000/78/EC), the Racial Equality Directive (2000/43/EC), the Equal Treatment in Goods and Services Directive (2004/113/EC) and the Gender Equality Directive (2006/54/EC).¹⁵

To guarantee compliance with the **rule of law**, systems developed for and deployed in border management and law enforcement must not interfere with the right to claim asylum, affect the presumption of innocence, the right to fair trial, and the right to defence, enshrined in these legal bases:

- Principle of non-refoulement (Art. 33 Geneva Refugee Convention and Protocol; Art 3. ECHR, through case law)
- Right to asylum (Art. 18 CFR)
- Right to have a fair trial (Art. 6 ECHR; Art. 47 CFR)
- No punishment without law (Art. 7 ECHR)
- Right to an effective remedy (Art. 13, ECHR; Art. 47 CFR)
- Presumption of innocence and right of defence (Art. 48 CFR)

To ensure the respect of the **social and economic rights** of persons working within border management and law enforcement, the systems provided for use in that context must also comply with:

- The right to work and to be appropriately trained (Art. 1 ESC)
- The right to just conditions of work (Art.2 ESC)
- The right to safe and healthy working conditions (Art. 2 ESC)
- The right to protection of health (Art. 11 ESC)

The **rights to privacy and data protection** are also considered fundamental rights and are therefore enshrined in the ECHR and CFR, namely:

- Right to respect for private and family life (Art. 8, ECHR; Art. 7 CFR)
- Right to protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR, Art. 16 TFEU)

Over the last decade comprehensive data protection legislation has been adopted by the EU and its Member States. For example, Convention 108+¹⁶, legally binds its signatories to comply with protections against potential abuse of human rights and fundamental freedoms. Convention 108+ places a particular focus on the legitimacy and transparency of data processing as they relate to the rights of the data subject in the context of increasing “diversification, intensification and globalisation of data processing and personal data flows”.¹⁷ This issue is of relevance to EINSTEIN, as future solutions are expected to support and enable privacy enhancing technologies, such as self-sovereign identity (SSI). The main data protection instrument, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹⁸ is the landmark legislative act governing data protection in the Union, in addition to the GDPR for European Union Institutions (GDPR for EUI)¹⁹, as well as the Law Enforcement Directive (LED)²⁰. Recent reports have highlighted the practical challenges of managing the relationship between the GDPR and LED.²¹ These acts are examined further below.

¹⁵ Council of the EU, 2000a and 2000b; Council of the EU, 2004b; Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2006.

¹⁶ Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to the Processing of Personal Data (CETS No.223, more commonly known as Convention 108+, a modernisation of CETS No. 108). See in particle Art 5 on the legitimacy of data processing and data quality; Art 7 on data security; Art 8 on the transparency of processing; and Art 9 on the rights of the data subject. Council of Europe, 1981.

¹⁷ Ibid., p.7.

¹⁸ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2016c.

¹⁹ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2018a.

²⁰ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2016a.

²¹ Vogiatzoglou and Marquenie, 2022; European Commission, 2022a.

3.2 Data protection

3.2.1 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The GDPR (Regulation 2016/679) imposes obligations to organisations that target or collect data related to individuals in the EU. It sets the framework for upholding the fundamental rights to privacy and data protection, harmonises the framework among MS, and holds accountable organisations processing data. Article 5 of the GDPR stipulates **seven principles** relating to the processing of personal data of the data subject (the individual, whose data is collected) by the data controller (the body that determines the purposes and essential means of processing, and the main body responsible for compliance with the GDPR) and data processor (a body who may processes data on behalf of the controller). As stated in Art. 5, personal data shall be:

- *“processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject (**‘lawfulness, fairness and transparency’**);*
- *collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes (...) (**‘purpose limitation’**);*
- *adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed (**‘data minimisation’**);*
- *accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay (**‘accuracy’**);*
- *kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed (...) (**‘storage limitation’**);*
- *processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures (**‘integrity and confidentiality’**).*
- *The controller shall be responsible for, and be able to demonstrate compliance (...) (**‘accountability’**).”²²*

These principles apply to all data collection in the EU that does not fall within the scope of the LED or the GDPR for EUI. These are context-specific acts that are largely built upon the same data protection principles as the GDPR.

Article 6 of the GDPR requires that the data processing must be set in one of the following legal bases:

- Data subject has given **consent** for processing of one or more specific purposes.
- Processing is necessary for the **performance of a contract** to which the data subject is a party.
- Processing is necessary for compliance with **legal obligation of controller**.
- Processing is necessary in order to protect vital interests of data subject or another natural person.
- Processing is necessary for a **task carried out in public interest** or in the exercise of official authority of a data controller.
- Processing is necessary for **the legitimate interests pursued by the controller** or a third party, except when such interests are overridden by fundamental rights and freedoms of data subjects.²³

The individual is then subject to several **rights**:

- Right of access
- Right to be informed (the data controller is obliged to inform data subjects how their data is processed and under which legal basis)
- Right to erasure (right to be forgotten)
- Right to object

²² Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2016c

²³ Ibid.

- Right to rectification
- Right to restrict processing
- Right to data portability
- Right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing, incl. profiling.²⁴

The GDPR is still retained in domestic law in the UK, as the Data Protection Act (DPA)²⁵. As one of the EINSTEIN partners is a UK entity (the UK Home Office) any data processing carried out will be done under the DPA. The protections and requirements between the GDPR and the DPA are the same. However, there are additional considerations to be taken into consider when transferring and sharing data (see section 3.2.3 for further details).

3.2.2 Law Enforcement Directive (LED)

The LED (Directive 2016/680)²⁶ governs the personal data processing by law enforcement authorities under two conditions: 1) that the data is processed by **competent authorities**, and 2) that it is processed for the **prevention, investigation, detection and prosecution of criminal offences**. The obligations for controllers under the LED mirror, to a large extent, the requirements enshrined in the GDPR. This includes implementing data protection by-design and by default, record-keeping, conducting data protection impact assessments (DPIAs), the security of processing, notification of data breaches and the appointment of a data protection officer (DPO), tasked with advising data protection compliance.²⁷ Controllers are obliged to maintain a record of logs when the processing operation is automated, which should comply with prompt accessibility in case of internal or supervisory audits. Whereas consultation and disclosure (i.e. sharing) logs should include date/time, officer identification and justification for the action [Art.25 LED].²⁸

Art 4 of the LED sets out the following principles on the processing of personal data, whereby personal data shall be:

- *processed lawfully and fairly;*
- *collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes;*
- *adequate, relevant and not excessive in relation to the purposes for which they are processed;*
- *accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay;*
- *kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which they are processed;*
- *processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures.²⁹*

Two of the crucial principles of the LED are purpose limitation and data minimisation. Data minimisation stipulates that data collected is 'adequate, relevant and not excessive' [Art.4 LED].³⁰ The wording used in the LED deviates from GDPR's 'adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary', providing LEAs with the flexibility necessary for safeguarding criminal procedures, such as investigations, where it may not be immediately evident what kind of data is used. The principle of purpose limitation, which guarantees that data is not used outside the context or the

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ UK Government, 2018.

²⁶ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2016a.

²⁷ Quintel, 2022; Vogiatzoglou and Marquenie, 2022.

²⁸ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2016c.

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Ibid.

public task for which they are gathered, dictates that personal data shall be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes related to law enforcement tasks, and, unlike the GDPR, does not forbid further processing for a divergent purpose,³¹ as Art. 4(2) LED permits further processing for another purpose (without requiring compatibility of the primary and secondary processing purposes) in so far as,

- they are processed for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, including the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security,
- the controller is authorised to process such data for such a purpose under EU and national law,
- the processing is necessary and proportionate,
- and subject to appropriate safeguards.³²

The principle of purpose limitation was intended to safeguard the informational division of powers, separating data processed by law enforcement and migration authorities, classifying them as different purposes. However, the practical realities of implementation, coupled with legislative initiatives to make the systems interoperable, make the application of the regulations challenging. The next sections outlines some of the key differences between the GDPR and the LED as they relates to privacy and data protection.

3.2.3 Comparative analysis of the GDPR and the LED

The GDPR provides for the security of processing by ways of pseudonymisation, encryption, confidentiality, and system resilience. However, the LED takes account of the difficulty to guarantee all these, providing instead a checklist of security measures for LEAs to adopt as data controllers when automated processing is involved:

- *deny unauthorised persons access to processing equipment used for processing ('equipment access control');*
- *prevent the unauthorised reading, copying, modification or removal of data media ('data media control');*
- *prevent the unauthorised input of personal data and the unauthorised inspection, modification or deletion of stored personal data ('storage control');*
- *prevent the use of automated processing systems by unauthorised persons using data communication equipment ('user control');*
- *ensure that persons authorised to use an automated processing system have access only to the personal data covered by their access authorisation ('data access control');*
- *ensure that it is possible to verify and establish the bodies to which personal data have been or may be transmitted or made available using data communication equipment ('communication control');*
- *ensure that it is subsequently possible to verify and establish which personal data have been input into automated processing systems and when and by whom the personal data were input ('input control');*
- *prevent the unauthorised reading, copying, modification or deletion of personal data during transfers of personal data or during transportation of data media ('transport control');*
- *ensure that installed systems may, in the case of interruption, be restored ('recovery');*
- *ensure that the functions of the system perform, that the appearance of faults in the functions is reported ('reliability') and that stored personal data cannot be corrupted by means of a malfunctioning of the system ('integrity').³³*

In addition, Art. 6 of the LED **distinguishes between different categories of data subject**: suspect, convicted person, victim, other party to an offence (witness, informer, associate, etc.). This distinction is important in justifying certain

³¹ De Hert and Sajfert, 2021.

³² Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2016c.

³³ Ibid.

collection and processing, and if a person is switched across categories LEAs are expected to update this information.

Both the GDPR (Art 9) and the LED (Art 10 and Art 11) allow the processing of sensitive personal data (racial, ethnic, political, religious and sexual identity, plus **biometrics**), so long as the relevant conditions are met. Of these conditions, the following are worth noting:

- Processing must be authorised by Union or Member State law,
- Processing must be strictly necessary (in line with the principle of necessity),
- Processing must be subject to appropriate safeguards for the rights and freedoms of the data subject,
- Processing relates to data which are manifestly made public by the data subject.³⁴

While the GDPR allows for consent as a legal basis for processing special categories of personal data, the LED (Art. 8) does not. Rather, a separate legal basis is required for processing of special category data under the LED, with consent serving as an additional safeguard. In addition, the issue of how 'manifestly made public by the data subject' is defined is of particular relevance to the processing of biometric data, as it is argued that the publication of a photograph does not mean that the biometric data, which can be retrieved from the photograph, has been manifestly made public.³⁵ The provision of adequate safeguards for processing of special categories of personal data is crucial, as any breach or misuse of the data could lead to significant consequences for the data subject, and by extension the controller.³⁶

Art 22 of the GDPR and Art 11 of the LED address the automated processing of personal and special category personal data. Both the GDPR and LED require that decisions based (solely) on automated processing are prohibited, unless authorised by Union or MS law and the necessary conditions and safeguards are met, including the right to obtain human intervention.³⁷ The transparency of automated decision-making differs significantly between the GDPR and LED, and must be assessed in proportion to public safety and security. Art. 13(1) LED stipulates data subjects' right to be informed and lists the information that is to be made available by the controller to any potential data subject, without having to reveal any processing techniques. This information could be published in an easy-to-understand, clear and plain language on the website of a police authority, border management agency or another authority competent under the LED. To allow the data subject to exercise their rights, the information should include the contact details of the controller and of the DPO, and the entitlement to a complaint procedure.³⁸ Art. 14(1) LED further enshrines the right of access, according to which the data subject has the right to obtain confirmation from the controller as to whether or not their data is being processed. Both the GDPR and the LED provide that for processing involving technologies considered high risk to fundamental rights, the controller should carry out a **Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)** before processing, in order to determine the risks and mitigation strategies, in consultation with their DPOs.

The delineation between the GDPR and the LED is a controversial topic. The scope of application of each instrument is intended to be seamless, however, this seems not to be the case in practice.³⁹ The GDPR is meant to apply for any 'general processing', whereas any 'law enforcement processing' should fall within the scope of the LED. Yet, in practice, such a distinction is difficult to delineate, which often leads to an overly broad interpretation of the LED in the transposition process.⁴⁰ This is often the case in border control, migration and asylum contexts for many EU MS. While legal scholars advise that for processing carried out in the context of migration, border control

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ European Data Protection Supervisor, 2023.

³⁶ See for example a recent fine imposed on the Greek Ministry for Migration and Asylum for breach of GDPR: https://www.edpb.europa.eu/news/national-news/2024/ministry-migration-and-asylum-receives-administrative-fine-and-gdpr_en.

³⁷ Quintel, 2022.

³⁸ Ibid.

³⁹ Ibid.

⁴⁰ Ibid.

and asylum, the GDPR should be applicable in a general manner subject to exceptions,⁴¹ in reality national legislation, transposition acts and LEAs themselves might choose to interpret border management as a law enforcement task, due to its presumed preventative nature with regard to irregular border crossing. This might also depend on the national law enforcement and border management structures, mandates and delineation of tasks, subject to constitutional and legal provisions.

In principle, the LED should only apply when both its personal and material scopes are satisfied. The personal scope requires a competent authority, which under Art. 3(7) refers to:

- *any public authority competent for the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, including the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security; or*
- *any other body or entity entrusted by Member State law to exercise public authority and public powers for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, including the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security.*⁴²

EINSTEIN's WP6 will conduct a legal analysis of the national frameworks of at least 3 different countries, including the project Pilot Use Cases (PUC) – the UK, the Netherlands, and the Greek/Bulgarian border, in order to ensure project activities are in full compliance with both the GDPR and the LED. The results of this analysis will be incorporated in future iterations of the IA, to ensure the development and deployment of the solutions is compliant with both EU and MS laws, and where relevant national legislators' discretion.

Art. 44 of the GDPR, allows for the transfer of personal data to third countries and international organisation only if the level of protection of natural persons guaranteed under the GDPR is not undermined. Transfers can be made on the basis of adequacy decisions (Art. 45) and/or appropriate safeguard have been provided, and on the condition that enforceable data subject right and effective legal remedies are available (Art. 46), derogations to these conditions are outlined in Art. 49. When it comes to exchanges of personal data between EU LEAs, the LEA from which the data originated cannot impose conditions on recipients in another EU LEA, other than those applicable within its own jurisdiction. Under Art 61 of the LED international agreements on data sharing with third countries and international organisations pre-dating the LED remain in force until amended. Therefore agreements need only to comply with the LED if amended after May 2018. In the context of border management, bilateral agreements with TCNs' countries of origin (including data adequacy decisions) continue to apply, whereas for new adequacy decisions (as is the case with the UK), a separate one is required for the LED. Data transfers with third countries should only be allowed between competent authorities under Art. 3(7) (i.e. LEAs acting as data controllers), subject to authorisation by the originating EU MS, whereas onward transfers must be approved from the originating state.⁴³ Finally, several derogations are provided in the LED, that are not part of the GDPR. For example, while Art. 37(1) LED offers fewer options to controllers to transfer personal data by way of appropriate safeguards than the GDPR, a self-assessment option provides leeway to the controller. Appropriate safeguards can be provided either in a legally binding instrument, such as an international agreement, or in the presence of an assessment by the controller of the circumstances surrounding the transfer, concluding that appropriate safeguards exist in the third country or international organisation. This self-assessment needs to be reported to the DPO by the controller, as well as documented. Furthermore, in the migration context, the competent authorities might argue for certain data transfers to occur under the LED, such as data on returns of rejected asylum seekers. Generally, an administrative task, under Art.37 LED, the personal data of a rejected asylum seeker who has also committed a crime could be transferred for both purposes conjointly under the LED.⁴⁴ After the UK's 2020 exit from the EU, it became a de facto third country, therefore the Union's data protection framework no longer applies. In order for information exchange to continue, the European Commission assessed the UK's national data protection legislation and issued two data adequacy decision in June 2021: one for the GDPR and one for the LED.⁴⁵ The adequacy decisions

⁴¹ Ibid.; De Hert and Sajfert, 2021.

⁴² Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2016c.

⁴³ Quintel, 2022.

⁴⁴ Ibid.

⁴⁵ European Commission, 2023.

essentially attest that the UK's GDPR system offers equivalent protections to the EU GDPR, allowing exchange of personal data to continue. The adequacy decisions, however, do not apply to transfers for the purposes of UK immigration control, the Commission will reassess the need for this exclusion once the situation has been remedied under UK law.⁴⁶ The Commission included a "sunset clause" to the decisions, limiting the duration of their validity to four years. This implies that in June 2025, the Commission needs to renew the adequacy decisions (pending assessment of the UK's evolving data protection framework) if it wishes to continue exchanging personal data with the UK.⁴⁷

3.1.2.3. GDPR for EUIs

Regulation (EU) 2018/1725,⁴⁸ also known as the GDPR for European Union Institutions (EUIs) governs the data processing carried out by EU institutions, bodies, offices and agencies. It is largely based on the GDPR's principles, while reinforcing some to accommodate the legal nature of the EU's public institutions. It strengthens accountability, obliging EUIs to demonstrate compliance by documentation of their personal data processing activities kept in a central register made publicly accessible (Art.31). In addition, it appoints a European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS), to ensure compliance and handle complaints from data subjects, as well as to carry out audits and impose administrative fines [Art.63, Art. 58(1)(b), Art.66]. The legal act mandates EUIs to employ privacy-by-design through a risk-based approach to data collection and processing activities [Art.26 and Rec. 38]. Finally, it establishes strict requirements regarding data breaches and obligations to notify the EDPS therein, within 72 hours of discovering them (Art.34).

Chapter IX sets out the obligations of EUIs when processing operational personal data which fall within the scope of Chapter 4 (Judicial cooperation in criminal matters) or Chapter 5 (police cooperation) of Title V of Part Three TFEU. This includes principles on the processing of operational personal data (Art 71) and the lawfulness of this processing (Art 72). Art 76 and 77, detail the processing of special category personal data and automated individual decision-making, including profiling, respectively. Articles 78-84, set out the rights of the data subject, and limitations to those rights. The safeguarding of data processing is established in Art 85 through to Art 93. And the transfer of operational data to third countries and international organisations is addressed under Art 94.

The EINSTEIN Applications will be deployed in an ecosystem of interoperability with many of the large-scale IT systems operated by EUIs. The implications of this for Application design and development will be assessed in future iterations of the IA, however this operating condition is being actively discussed.

3.3 AI Act

Adopted by the Council of the EU on 14 May 2024, Regulation 2024/1689 (AI Act)⁴⁹, is the first comprehensive regulatory act on Artificial Intelligence (AI). It applies to any AI products developed on or entering the European market, and undertakes a risk-based approach to regulating AI systems.

It considers the following systems to carry "unacceptable risk" due to their risk for violating fundamental rights, rendering them prohibited among others:

- Cognitive behavioural manipulation of people or specific vulnerable groups (e.g. voice-activated toys encouraging dangerous behaviour in children)
- Social scoring: classifying people based on behaviour, socio-economic status or personal characteristics (on the basis of sensitive personal data)
- Biometric identification and categorisation of people on the basis of sensitive personal data (incl. law enforcement profiling on the basis of these)

⁴⁶ Ibid.

⁴⁷ Andreeva, 2023, p.67.

⁴⁸ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2018a.

⁴⁹ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2024c.

- Real-time and remote biometric identification systems in public spaces, such as facial recognition (e.g. CCTV), except for specific necessary law enforcement objectives.⁵⁰

AI systems that are likely to negatively affect safety or fundamental rights will be considered “high risk”⁵¹ including:

- 1) AI systems used in products under the EU’s product safety legislation (e.g. toys, aviation, cars, medical devices and lifts)
- 2) AI systems falling into the areas listed below will have to be registered in an EU database maintained by the Commission:
 - Biometrics
 - Safety components in the management and operation of critical infrastructure
 - Education and vocational training
 - Employment, workers’ management and access to self-employment
 - Access to and enjoyment of essential private services and essential public services and benefits
 - Law enforcement
 - Migration, asylum and border control management
 - Administration of justice and democratic processes. [Annex III, AI Act]⁵²

Annex III specifies that remote biometric identification systems, as well as systems intended for biometric categorisation and emotion recognition are to be considered high-risk, however systems intended solely for biometric verification of a natural person are excluded from this categorisation. AI systems classified as “high-risk” will be assessed before entering the market and also throughout their lifecycle. They will be subject to further requirements and oversight, while citizens will have the right to file complaints about these to designated national authorities. In principle, an AI system designed to aid in the profiling of natural persons should be considered high-risk.

3.3.1 Requirements for high-risk systems

Under the AI Act, high-risk systems are assigned additional obligations, including:

- Risk management system

High-risk AI systems need to provide a risk management system, interpreted by the AI Act as a “continuous iterative process planned and run throughout the entire lifecycle of a high-risk AI system, requiring regular systematic review and updating” [Section 2, Art.9]. This involves identification and analysis of “reasonably foreseeable risks” to health, safety or fundamental rights, when the system is used for its intended purpose. These and other possible risks need to be evaluated and “appropriate and targeted” mitigation measures need to be provided. As much as “technically feasible”, those risks should be eliminated, while adequate information on those should be provided to users.⁵³

- Data and data governance

Training, validation and testing datasets used in the development of an AI system, should be subject to data management practices, which should consider the origin and purposes of collection of the data used, data preparation processing operations (e.g. annotation, labelling, cleaning, updating, enrichment, aggregation), formulation of assumptions on the basis of what the data represents and can measure, an identification of data gaps or shortcomings, as well as an examination of possible biases of the data that can risk discrimination, and

⁵⁰ Some exceptions will apply for law enforcement purposes; “real-time” remote biometric identification systems will be allowed for investigation of serious cases, while “post” remote biometric identification systems, where identification occurs after a significant delay, will be allowed to prosecute serious crimes and only after court approval. (European Parliament, 2023)

⁵¹ See Annex 1 for further details.

⁵² Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2024c.

⁵³ Ibid.

appropriate measures provided to prevent and mitigate potential biases. [Art.10]. Further conditions apply for the processing of special categories of personal data:

- *the bias detection and correction **cannot be effectively fulfilled by processing other data, including synthetic or anonymised data**;*
- *the special categories of personal data are subject to technical limitations on the re-use of the personal data, and state-of-the-art security and **privacy-preserving measures, including pseudonymisation**;*
- *the special categories of personal data are subject to measures to ensure that the personal data processed are **secured, protected, subject to suitable safeguards**, including strict controls and documentation of the access, to avoid misuse and ensure that only authorised persons with appropriate confidentiality obligations have access to those personal data;*
- *the personal data in the special categories of personal data are **not to be transmitted**, transferred or otherwise accessed by other parties;*
- *the personal data in the special categories of personal data are **deleted once the bias has been corrected** or the personal data has reached the **end of its retention period**, whichever comes first;*
- *the **records** of processing activities pursuant to Regulations (EU) 2016/679 and (EU) 2018/1725 and Directive (EU) 2016/680 include **the reasons why the processing of special categories of personal data was strictly necessary** to detect and correct biases, and why that objective could not be achieved by processing other data.⁵⁴*

- Technical documentation

Technical documentation demonstrating compliance with the AI Act requirements should be drawn up before it is placed on the market, whereas SMEs and start-ups are subject to simpler documentation provided by the Commission [Art.11].⁵⁵

- Record-keeping (logging)

High-risk AI systems should technically enable the automatic logging of events over their lifetime, which should allow for identifying situations that present a risk to health, safety or fundamental rights, and facilitating the monitoring of the system's operation and interaction with other AI systems. The logging should provide a recording of the time periods of each use of the system, the reference database it used, the data against which it concluded on a match, and the identification of humans involved in the verification. [Art.12].⁵⁶

- Transparency and provision of information to users

High-risk AI systems should be designed to ensure their operation is transparent, enabling deployers to interpret its output and use it appropriately. This includes providing deployers with appropriate and comprehensible digital instructions for use. Such instructions should contain the identity and contact details of the provider and the "characteristics, capabilities and limitations of performance" of the AI. Instructions should also inform of planned changes to the system at the stage of conformity assessment, human oversight measures, computational and hardware resources necessary to deploy and maintain the system, and a description of the mechanisms allowing the system's deployers to collect, store and interpret logs [Art.13].⁵⁷

- Human oversight

While human oversight is essential for all AI systems operating in the EU, high-risk systems will be subject to higher scrutiny. Oversight measures should aim to prevent or minimise the risks to health, safety and fundamental rights, and should be commensurate with the levels of risk, autonomy and the context of the system's use. The measures

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ Ibid.

⁵⁶ Ibid.

⁵⁷ Ibid.

should be implemented either before the system is placed on the market and/or before deployment if they are to be implemented by the deployer. Those charged with oversight should be enabled to:

- Understand the capacity and limitations of the system sufficiently, so as to allow them to monitor its operation and detect "anomalies, dysfunction and unexpected performance";
- Be aware of the potential for automation bias, i.e. the tendency for over-reliance on the output of automated AI systems intended to aid human decision-making;
- Correctly interpret the output of the high-risk system through various interpretation methods;
- Decide at any time to disregard the AI system's output;
- Intervene and stop the operation of the high-risk system in a safe way.

While the AI Act further obliges the deployers of high-risk systems used for remote biometric identification to verify its result against two human evaluators with the necessary expertise [Art. 14(5)], it provides an exception if such systems are used "for the purposes of law enforcement, migration, border control or asylum", as it considers the burden of implementing such a requirement to be "disproportionate" in these domains [Art.14(5) and Annex III, 1(a)].⁵⁸

- Accuracy, robustness, cybersecurity

While all AI systems in the EU are expected to guarantee technical robustness and cyber-security, the requirements for high-risk systems are stricter. The Commission commits to develop appropriate metrics and benchmarks for technical accuracy and robustness with relevant stakeholders.⁵⁹ The AI Act mandates that technical and organisational measures be taken to make high-risk systems resilient to errors and inconsistencies, whereas accuracy metrics should be declared in the user instructions. Measures suggested for achieving robustness are technical redundancy solutions, incl. backup or fail-safe plans. High-risk AI systems that continue to learn after being placed on the market, should aim to eliminate or significantly reduce "feedback loops", (defined as "the risk of possibly biased outputs influencing input for future operations"). Finally, high-risk AI systems should be resilient against potential cyber-attacks or unauthorised third parties' interference in their operation. Measures to ensure such resilience should target detection and response to "data poisoning" (attacks aimed at manipulating the dataset), "model poisoning" (via pre-trained components used during training phases), inputs designed to make the model to conduct an error ("adversarial examples and "model evasion"), as well as confidentiality attacks and model flaws [Art.15].⁶⁰

The full text of requirements of high-risk AI systems are listed in **Annex 5**.

In addition to the general requirements for high-risk AI systems, the AI Act provides a list **of obligations for the providers** (in the case of EINSTEIN technical partners) **and deployers** (in the case of EINSTEIN LEAs and border management agencies) for the deployment of high-risk AI systems:

- Quality management system (provider)
- Documentation keeping (provider)
- Automatically generated logs (provider)
- Conformity assessment (provider and importer)
- EU declaration of conformity (provider)
- Registration obligation (provider)
- Information of national competent authority upon request (provider)
- Affix CE marking (Article 49) (importer and distributor)
- Corrective actions and duty of information (Article 21) (provider)
- Demonstrate conformity upon request (provider, importer and distributor)
- Comply with instructions for use (deployer)
- Consider relevance & quality of input data (deployer)

⁵⁸ Ibid.

⁵⁹ See, for example, [The Working Group on Interoperable Benchmarking of AI systems](#).

⁶⁰ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2024c.

- Monitor operation of the system (deployer)
- Execution of data protection impact assessment (deployer).⁶¹

Compliance with the requirements for high-risk AI systems vis-à-vis these obligations for providers and deployers will be monitored as part of the translation of ELSI risks and opportunities into requirements under T2.3, and as part of the wider EINSTEIN Application testing and development process. This initial IA provides a provisional classification of each Application as per the risk levels of the AI Act (see Section 4.2), to be reassessed in future iterations of this assessment, on the basis of the development process.

The AI Act will take effect from the 01 August 2024 and will be fully applicable 24 months after entry into force. However some parts of the legislation will be applicable sooner, such as the ban of AI systems posing unacceptable risk (applicable 6 months after entry into force), codes of practice (applicable 9 months after entry into force) and rules on transparency that general-purpose AI models need to comply with (applicable 12 months after entry into force). High-risk systems will have more time to ensure compliance with the new obligations as they are applicable 36 months after entry into force.⁶²

It is important to note that the AI Act does not apply to any research, testing or development activity regarding AI systems or models prior to their being placed on the market or put into service. [Art. 2(8)]. However, the testing of AI systems in real-world conditions is not covered by the scientific research exemption of the AI Act, therefore EINSTEIN will pay particular attention to the applicable requirements for testing the project's applications, and to the post-project exploitation of the tools developed in operational conditions. In addition, as EINSTEIN is an Innovation Action aiming for high TRL, the design actions taken now should aim to be compliant with the AI Act to avoid unnecessary re-design in the future. Therefore, partners will ensure the foresight compliance of project activities, in anticipation of the solutions' potential post-project deployment.

3.4 The Digital Identity Management Ecosystem

The EINSTEIN Applications will be deployed into a wider ecosystem of digital identity management for both border control and law enforcement purposes. Digital identity management draws on both existing legislative initiatives, as well as new and ongoing developments that aim to construct the technical, legal, and social infrastructure that will support secure, robust and socially beneficial digital identity management processes. The following sections outline some of the key legal frameworks defining the digital identity management ecosystem, which the EINSTEIN Applications will need to take into consideration.

The International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) has established specifications for two types of document for international travel: (1) a machine-readable travel document (MRTD) has a standardised format, incl. identification details of the holder, a photograph/digital image and other mandatory and optional elements, and (2) an electronic MRTD (eMRTD), which must also contain a contactless integrated circuit chip with an antenna, storing data from the electronic data page and biometric data (fingerprints and facial image) of the passport holder.⁶³ The integration of biometrics in passports and travel documents aims to improve document security and prevent falsification of documents through more reliable checks. A digital signature on an ePassport is derived from the issuing State's security certificates— the Country Signing Certification Authority (CSCA) Certificate and the Document Signer Certificate (DSC). Together, the signature and certificates form a trust chain as one is securely anchored in the authority of the issuing State and the other end is securely stored in the chip of the ePassport as the Document Security Object.⁶⁴ At BCPs, border control systems retrieve the Document Security Object from the chip and checks it against the DSC and the CSCA certificate, in which case it is deemed validated. The standardised biometrics

⁶¹ Ibid.

⁶² Ibid.

⁶³ International Civil Aviation Organisation 2021a and 2021b; International Civil Aviation Organisation 1944; International Civil Aviation Organisation, 2016.

⁶⁴ International Civil Aviation Organisation, n.d.

currently used for ePassports are facial images, fingerprints, and iris recognition (optional under Extended Access Control, (EAC)). ICAO defines the biometric file formats and communication protocols to be used in passports, whereas document and chip characteristics are documented in ICAO Doc 9303.⁶⁵ Such standards imply interoperability between different issuers and manufacturers of passport books. Only the digital image (usually in JPEG or JPEG 2000 format) of each biometric feature is actually stored in the chip. The comparison of biometric features is performed outside the passport chip by electronic border control systems. The ICAO standard describes some security requirements that partly conform to the European law on the provision of security mechanisms.⁶⁶ Some security mechanisms currently in use are:

- Biometric passport with Basic Access Control (BAC): Protects against reading the passport without the holder's permission. Without BAC, ePassport contents could be potentially read when the holder least expects.
- Biometric passport with Extended Access Control (EAC): Restricts access to certain elements of e-passport contents to authorised parties (e.g. border control). This capability serves to protect fingerprints, iris scans, etc. This passport is based on asymmetric cryptographic protocols and uses stronger encryption.
- Biometric passport with Supplemental Access Control (SAC): Aimed at ensuring the future-proof security of electronic travel documents. It ensures the contactless chip cannot be read without physical access to the travel document while the data exchange between the chip and reading device is encrypted.⁶⁷

Under current ICAO standards only facial image and fingerprints could be contained in ePassports. However, under Logical Data Structure 2 (LDS2), an optional and backwards compatible extension of the ePassport chip, the ability to retroactively include additional biometrics is currently under review as part of standardisation work.⁶⁸ The adoption of LDS2 changes the ePassport from a read-only document to one that can be re-written and extends its use, as it allows it to securely store electronic visas, travel stamps and additional biometrics (iris and fingerprint), post-issuance. Nevertheless, this new voluntary framework may cause inconsistencies as not all Member States may choose to implement it, while increasing some privacy risks. On the other hand, it will include the additional information needed to systematically check passengers using Automated Border Control (ABC) Systems, while reliably standardising travel data that can aid in on-the-spot risk assessment for border management agents, while improving passenger flow at BCPs.⁶⁹ The legal basis for including biometric identifiers in the passports and travel documents of EU nationals is Regulation 2252/2004/EC with amended Regulation (EC) 444/2009 for the purpose of verifying the document's authenticity and the holder's identity.⁷⁰ The EINSTEIN Applications will need to be interfaced with ePassport, and so will need to stay cognisant of any developments to the content and security requirements of ePassports, in addition to other identity document types.

Work is ongoing to establish **Digital Travel Credentials (DTC)**. DTCs are electronic identity documents, which can temporarily or permanently substitute paper identification, reducing waiting times at border crossings. The DTC consists of a virtual component (DTC-VC), which contains the digital representation of the traveller's identity, and a physical component (DTC-PC), cryptographically linked to the virtual component.⁷¹ DTCs will be implemented along three typologies:

- DTC Type 1 (eMRTD Bound) is generated by the user directly on a smartphone or from a self-service kiosk by reading the chip in the passport, wherein the passport is the physical component.
- DTC Type 2 (eMRTD-PC Bound) is issued and digitally signed by a passport issuing authority, linked to the passport and possibly to other physical components, through cryptographic mechanisms.
- DTC Type 3 (PC Bound) has its own life cycle, as it is issued and digitally signed by an issuing authority independently of a passport linked with a physical component (e.g. smartphone).

⁶⁵ International Civil Aviation Organisation, 2021b.

⁶⁶ Kolan and Thapaliya, 2011.

⁶⁷ International Civil Aviation Organisation, n.d.

⁶⁸ Ikura and Kinneging 2016.

⁶⁹ Ibid.

⁷⁰ Council of the EU, 2004a, Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2009a.

⁷¹ International Civil Aviation Organisation, 2020a; eu-LISA, 2022b, p.36.

DTC Type 1 Specifications and guiding principles have been published (ICAO,2020) as have DTC virtual component data structure and public key infrastructure (PKI) mechanisms (ICAO, 2020) and are currently under implementation.⁷² DTC Type 2 and 3 will be compatible with Type 1, and their implementation will be based on the same guidelines. Some of the differences between the three DTC types are visualised in the image below.

	DTC Type 1	DTC Type 2	DTC Type 3
Passport booklet and smartphone			
Description	The DTC on the mobile device is a representation of the same data that can be found on the chip of the passport.	The DTC on the mobile device is equivalent to the physical passport.	The DTC on the mobile device is the only source of traveler information, with no reference to a physical document. This third level is relevant for temporary emergency travel documents.
Status of ICAO standardization	Technical specifications: certified in September 2020	Technical specifications: certification expected in 2022	Technical specifications: certification expected after 2022
Physical component	eMRTD	Mobile device and eMRTD (passport for reference purposes only)	Mobile device, temporary emergency documents.
Virtual component	Mobile device/cloud	Mobile device/cloud	Mobile device/cloud
Relationship between the physical and the virtual component	The physical component is the passport. The virtual component is composed of the data contained in the chip (Data groups 1 and 2).	Cryptographic link between the physical component, the smartphone, and the virtual component, composed of the data contained in the chip.	Cryptographic link between the physical component, the smartphone, and the virtual component, issued by the passport authority. The passport is no longer used.
DTC enrollment and issuance processes	Remote Anytime, anywhere. Biometric enrollment and Presentation Attack Detection (PAD) are recommended to prevent identity fraud and increase trust in the DTC.	In-person Face-to-face process. Supervision by a member of the city hall is advised. Biometric enrollment is recommended for a fully paperless journey.	Remote The traveler receives the DTC directly from the travel document issuing authority. Biometric enrollment and PAD are required to prevent identity fraud and to increase the level of security.
DTC uses	Depending on the journey, the traveler will be able to go through touchpoints by simply using their smartphone and biometrics. However, they must show their passport at least once, for example, at border control.	The traveler uses only their smartphone or biometrics to prove their identity through all touchpoints.	For emergency documents, the traveler may only need to present their smartphone or biometrics to prove their identity.

Figure 2: Types of DTCs and their specifications.⁷³

Based on ICAO DTC Type 1, the EU launched an initiative to digitalise travel documents to guarantee global compatibility of the standard. This included a consultation and pilot project on the submission and inspection process, the verification of identity, and the efficiency and security of entry into Schengen via DTCs.⁷⁴ A legislative proposal is expected in the near future. DTCs are expected to enable seamless travel, improve advance travel authorisation, streamline border management (especially after the launch of the EES and ETIAS), and can serve as emergency travel documents.

The eIDAS Regulation ("electronic IDentification, Authentication and trust Services")⁷⁵ oversees electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the EU. It regulates electronic signatures, transactions, certificates, e-commerce, etc., providing such services with a trust mark qualification, signalling their security for both the signatory and recipient. eIDAS established standards for electronic signatures, qualified digital certificates, electronic seals, timestamps, and other proof for authentication mechanisms enabling electronic transactions, with

⁷² eu-LISA, 2022b, p.37. International Civil Aviation Organisation, 2020a and 2020b.

⁷³ Idemia, 2021, p.7.

⁷⁴ eu-LISA, 2022b, p.38.

⁷⁵ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2014, European Commission, 2024.

the same legal standing as paper transactions. Furthermore, it ensures mutual recognition of electronic identifications (eIDs) across the EU. In April 2024, the proposed the **European Digital Identity (EUDI) Regulation**⁷⁶ was adopted, amending the eIDAS regulation by mandating EU MS to develop national electronic identification.⁷⁷ The EUDI Regulation aims to establish a secure European framework for a digital identity wallet, based on the eIDAS infrastructure. It will mandate EU MS to offer citizens and businesses digital identity wallets, which can link their national digital identities with proof of other identity attributes such as driving licenses, diplomas and bank accounts. The wallets will be issued by both public and private authorities and will aim to eliminate unnecessary data sharing by empowering users to decide which data they want to share. It will establish a harmonised approach across the EU, including in compliance with cybersecurity requirements.⁷⁸ Four large-scale pilot projects on digital identity wallets aim to explore solutions in areas such as application for identity documents, presenting travel documents to streamline border crossing and customs, managing payments, proof of education certifications, access to social security systems, etc. The EINSTEIN Applications will need to be compliant with specifications for the digital wallet, this includes integrating privacy preserving and privacy enhancing techniques into their design, such as **self-sovereign identity (SSI)**. SSI is a novel eIDAS-compliant approach to managing digital identities, that aims to provide individuals with more control over the data they use online and in their interactions with websites, services and applications. It enables users to manage their data in a decentralised way, without depending on third-party providers to store and centrally manage it, allowing users to share only the parts of the data necessary for each transaction. SSIs are considered a safer, cost-effective way both for consumers and for businesses and public authorities to share necessary data fast, while reducing costs, paper use and complying with GDPR.⁷⁹ In addition, to SSI the EINSTEIN Applications will integrate additional privacy-enhancing technologies, this includes non-centralized architectures based on blockchain and federated learning, which will be compliant with and extend the features of the new eID ecosystems. **Federated learning** supports the cross-border collaboration between organisations from different countries through the minimisation of personal data sharing, while the relevant data (e.g., trained models) is facilitated. In order to further enhance cybersecurity and privacy preservation, and to be qualified according to the requirements for eID, EINSTEIN will provide an integration with an **European Blockchain Services Infrastructure (EBSI)** ledger. A blockchain is a distributed ledger with growing lists of records (blocks) that are securely linked together via cryptographic hashes. Blockchain transactions are irreversible in that, once they are recorded, the data in any given block cannot be altered retroactively without altering all subsequent blocks, making this distributed computing system secure by design. EINSTEIN will also use privacy-enhancing biometrics binding to attributes in Verifiable Credentials and the privacy-friendly verification identity of the attribute holder, with techniques to mitigate privacy risk of 1:1 verification systems and explore privacy-enhancing techniques for 1:N biometric comparison.

The shift to remote ID management raises certain potential risks and vulnerabilities. ENISA's 2023 report on "Remote ID proofing good practices" offers strategies to mitigate these risks.⁸⁰ The report presents the most common types of attacks on remote identity proofing systems. The development of the EINSTEIN Applications will take account of such risks and follow state-of-the-art guidance as it becomes available.

Of particular relevance to EINSTEIN are efforts to digitalise travel. By incorporating digitalisation strategies for the public sector and digital identity and privacy-preserving technologies, the EU aims to achieve seamless travel, which entails digitalising border management procedures, such as identification, enrolment of data and automated border control.⁸¹ Achieving seamless travel involves several steps, including:

- Fully **digitalising the Schengen visa procedure** by 2025, by digitalising the visa application process and the visa sticker.⁸²

⁷⁶ Regulation (EU) 2024/1183, Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2024b.

⁷⁷ European Commission, 2024.

⁷⁸ Ibid.

⁷⁹ TNO, n.d.

⁸⁰ See Annex 3 for further details.

⁸¹ eu-LISA, 2022a.

⁸² EU Pact on Migration and Asylum (European Commission, 2020); eu-LISA, 2022b.

- **Providing Automated Border Control (ABC) Systems**, which authenticate the eMRTD or a travel token, establish that the traveller is the rightful holder therein, prompts the border control systems necessary, and determines whether the passenger is eligible to cross, on the basis of predefined rules.⁸³ ABC systems, such as egates have been implemented for citizens eligible to freedom of movement in the Schengen area and will soon be available to TCN under the EES.⁸⁴
- **Enabling Digital Travel Credentials (DTC)** as well as pre-border checks for sea and land borders to facilitate pre-arrival background checks, wherein carriers are responsible for ensuring that travellers are in possession of valid travel documents before entering the Schengen Area.
- Implementing **Innovations in enrolment of biometric data and self-service technologies** to reduce waiting times at border crossings after the introduction of the EES and ETIAS. The seamless travel process as envisioned is visualised in the image below.

Figure 3: Seamless travel as foreseen by eu-LISA.⁸⁵

EINSTEIN will contribute to several of these steps, namely the processes surrounding pre-checks by a carrier, pre-enrolment at a self-service kiosk and automated border control. To do so, the EINSTEIN Applications will need to

⁸³ Frontex, 2016; eu-LISA, 2022b, p.41.

⁸⁴ eu-LISA, 2022b.

⁸⁵ Ibid., p.15.

comply with existing EU (and corresponding national) legislation regulating border-crossing of EU citizens and TCNs in the Schengen area. The relevant legal acts governing this, as well as the information systems in aid of border management and internal security are outlined below.

The EU Visa Code⁸⁶ sets the rules for application and issuance of Schengen visas, issued to TCNs for a maximum of 90 days. The MS hosting issues the visas and the application must take place in person where fingerprints are to be collected (when applying for the first time). The applicant must demonstrate where and how long they intend to stay, the financial means they have for the stay and the intention to leave on time. Multiple-entry visas may also be issued to TCNs who have previously complied with visa regulations. The Visa Code was reformed in 2019, changing the prices of visas, the conditions for multiple-entry visas and the providing the possibility to apply electronically.⁸⁷

The Schengen Borders Code⁸⁸ sets out the rules for crossing Schengen borders. While all persons and goods are checked, EU citizens and other persons enjoying the right to free movement undergo minimum checks (verifying their identity and the validity of their travel document).⁸⁹ TCNs are subjected to thorough checks, wherein beyond the verification of their identity, their compliance with conditions for entry and stay in the Schengen area is checked (e.g. visa, justification of the purpose of the stay, availability of sufficient funds for subsistence throughout the expected stay, checks for related alerts in SIS, etc.) [Art.8]. In 2017, the Schengen Borders Code was amended to provide for systematic checks against relevant databases⁹⁰ (namely SIS and Interpol's SLTD) on all persons, including those enjoying the right of free movement when they cross any external border (air, sea and land), both at entry and exit.⁹¹ The amending act provides that if systematic checks lead to a disproportionate impact on border crossing points' traffic flows at sea and land borders, these can be reduced to targeted checks against databases, provided it would not impact internal security or public health.⁹² At air borders such derogation was only allowed for a transitional period of 6 months (extendable to 18 months) from the Regulation's entry into force. In 2022, the Commission concluded that systematic checks did lead to increased waiting times at BCPs, however judged those to be proportional to the benefits of internal security.⁹³

No border checks are allowed at the internal borders of the Schengen area, except in cases where a temporary reinstatement of border controls is authorised. Nevertheless, this is without prejudice to police powers of competent authorities, insofar as these do not have the effect of border checks, meaning that they:

- do not have border control as an objective;
- are based on information regarding possible threats to public security and aim to combat cross-border crime;
- are executed differently from systematic checks, and
- are carried out on the basis of spot-checks [Art.23(a)].⁹⁴

Compliance with the checks set out in the SBC are achieved through the development of multiple databases to collect and store alphanumeric and biometric data. **The EU's Large-Scale IT Systems** were designed as compensatory measures for the lifting of internal border controls in the Schengen Area. Initially foreseen to be strictly separated for usage by either law enforcement (and border control authorities) or by immigration authorities, these information systems have changed scope since the reform of the Schengen Borders Code and the

⁸⁶ Regulation (EC) No 810/2009, Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2009b.

⁸⁷ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2019c.

⁸⁸ Regulation (EU) 2016/399, Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2016d.

⁸⁹ Including the legitimate possession of the travel document.

⁹⁰ Whereas before the amending act, systematic checks were only obligatory for TCNs, and only upon entry into the Schengen area. Council of the EU, 2017.

⁹¹ Regulation (EU) 2017/458; Council of the EU, 2017.

⁹² Ibid.

⁹³ European Commission, 2022c.

⁹⁴ Council of the EU, 2017.

introduction of the interoperability legislation. The following overview will clarify the legal framework and intended usage (and users) of these systems, while stipulating the relevance to EINSTEIN.

The Schengen Information System (SIS-II)⁹⁵ is the largest law enforcement database in the EU, intended for detecting and investigating cross-border criminality. It supports the exchange of information between LEAs on people (suspects, missing persons, aliases) and objects (vehicles, weapons, lost or stolen identity documents⁹⁶, etc.). Through introducing alerts, LEAs are able to obtain cross-matches or “hits”, enabling more effective cross-border investigations. The operation of SIS is managed by national SIRENE bureaux, responsible for coordinating input and cross-border activities related to alerts. In 2018, eu-LISA launched the Automated Fingerprint Identification System (AFIS), which introduced a biometric search capability in SIS, allowing for the identification of persons solely using fingerprints, while the system also supports, palm marks and in some cases DNA records. The 2018 SIS upgrade also empowered Europol, Eurojust, Frontex, and national migration management support teams, dealing with irregular migration and returns, to have access to SIS.⁹⁷ Finally, the upgrade introduced by 2021 new types of alerts, including return decisions.

While none of EINSTEIN’s applications are designed to assist active police investigations, the data formats they support should be compatible with law enforcement systems such as SIS, in case border management or police officers using the applications discover an investigative lead on which that they need to consult other systems.

The Visa Information System (VIS)⁹⁸ is an EU-wide information system containing data related to short-term Schengen visas (incl. transit), composed of a central element (CS-VIS) managed by eu-LISA, national systems (N-VIS), managed by individual EU MS, and a communication infrastructure connecting these, operated by eu-LISA. It performs biometric matching on the basis of fingerprints and connects consulates in non-EU countries and all external border crossing points of Schengen states. In 2021, the VIS was reformed to strengthen background checks on applicants before issuing a visa, requiring EU MS to collect a facial image and 10 fingerprints for storage in VIS.⁹⁹ Only facial images taken live can be used for biometric matching, as this is considered to decrease the risk of face morphing. The data must be automatically deleted 5 years after the expiry date of the visa, and upon the expiration date (or exit) for children under 12 years old. Finally, the new legal basis will enable automated checks of SIS, Eurodac, EES, ETIAS, some Europol data and Interpol’s database on Stolen and Lost Documents (SLTD).¹⁰⁰ VIS will be interoperable with the EES, and so is directly related to the development of Application 5 – EES kiosk with advanced fraud detection. In addition, visa management has been targeted as a priority domain for digitalisation, this will require supporting measures, such as MAD and PAD, to ensure the security of the process.

Eurodac (European Asylum Dactyloscopy Database)¹⁰¹ is the EU’s system for registering asylum seekers and irregular border-crossers. It stores the fingerprints and photographs of asylum seekers over the age of 6, as well as previous asylum applications, refused entries and transits. Through the Automated Fingerprint Identification System (AFIS) authorities check whether asylum seekers have already applied for asylum in another EU member state or have illegally transited through another EU Member State as per the principle of first contact. Eurodac, however cannot store facial images or biographic data (name, place, date of birth).¹⁰² In 2024, a reformed legal basis was adopted extending Eurodac’s scope including the possibility for EU MS to store and search data belonging to third-country nationals or stateless persons who are not applicants for international protection and found irregularly staying in the EU, so that they can be identified for return and readmission purposes.¹⁰³ It will also allow the centralised storage of biographic data and identity and travel documents in Eurodac, while law enforcement and Europol are able to search Eurodac to prevent, detect or investigate a serious crime or terrorist offence.¹⁰⁴

⁹⁵ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2018c.

⁹⁶ Also covered in INTERPOL’s Lost and Stolen Passport Database (SLTD).

⁹⁷ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2018c.

⁹⁸ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2008.

⁹⁹ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2021.

¹⁰⁰ eu-LISA, 2022b, p.35.

¹⁰¹ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2013.

¹⁰² Thales Group, 2023.

¹⁰³ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2024d; European Parliament, 2024.

¹⁰⁴ Ibid.

Advance Passenger Information (API)¹⁰⁵ relates to information regarding passengers, which carriers are obliged to submit to authorised border crossing points at the Schengen area's external borders. The information comprises identity and travel documents used and the data therein, the BCP of entry, mode of transport, departure and arrival time of the transportation, total number of passengers carried on that transport and the initial point of embarkation. The updated API legal basis adopted in May 2024¹⁰⁶ sets uniform rules for API data collection, including better data quality and streamlined transmission, compulsory collection for all flights to the Schengen area for border management purposes and compulsory collection for law enforcement purposes on flights leaving the Schengen area.¹⁰⁷ It will also harmonise the API data collection with the EU PNR one, by transmitting data automatically through a single router, which will be the mandatory method of transmitting PNR data, however including provisions forbidding the use of API data in profiling.

EU Passenger Name Records (EU PNR)¹⁰⁸ allows the collection of data on all air travel passengers entering and leaving the EU (possible but not obligatory for intra-EU flights), where such data is provided to law enforcement authorities by airline carriers. The data transmitted is to be found on the passenger's reservation (names, dates of travel, luggage), although Recital 20 specifies that processing should not take place on the basis of special category data (race, ethnic origin, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, trade union membership, health or sexual orientation etc). As a decentralised database, it requires EU MS to build their own national infrastructures and Passenger Information Units (PIUs) responsible for the exchanges and compliance with the Directive. The initial retention period is six months, after which PNR data needs to be depersonalised by PIUs, meaning masking out names, addresses and contact information, payment information, frequent flyer information, general remarks and all API data (Art.12). This process should not be confused with anonymisation, as the data could be re-identifiable and may still be used for criminal law purposes under 'very strict and limited conditions' (Recital 25). It is important to note that, unlike API data, PNR data is provided by the passenger and is therefore considered unverified and potentially unreliable. Until the API reform PNR data collection was not obliged beyond the business purposes of air carriers (i.e. data on the traveller's reservation), meaning that some data collected could not be used by law enforcement authorities.¹⁰⁹ Currently there are ongoing negotiations on the introduction of PNR in other modes of travel (e.g. railway).¹¹⁰

European travel information and authorization system (ETIAS)¹¹¹ will be a pre-travel authorisation system for the short stay of third-country nationals who do not require a visa. It will not require biometric data, instead travellers will be required to submit their application forms online using either the official ETIAS website or the official mobile app before commencing their trip. It will enable border authorities to pre-assess the eligibility of visa exempt TCNs to enter and the length of their allowed stay in the Schengen area. Together with the EES, it is part of the EU's Smart Borders Package, aimed at centralised tracking of irregular stays.¹¹²

The Entry/Exit system (EES)¹¹³ will be an automated information system replacing passport stamping in the registration of all third-country nationals entering or leaving the EU, and will require identity and travel document check, as well as collection of biometric data (up to 4 fingerprints¹¹⁴ for visa-exempt TCNs and facial images for all TCNs), while recording entry and exit locations.¹¹⁵ Fingerprint data for visa-exempt TCNs will be stored in the EES, while visa-holders' fingerprints will remain only in VIS, however the EES will collect personal information from VIS and ETIAS as well. Records of entries, exits, and refusals of entry (incl. personal data) will be kept for 3 years, (from the date of recording), if no exit has been recorded data will be kept for 5 years, starting on the expiry date of the authorised stay. After the retention period the data should be automatically deleted. The EES is targeted at tracking

¹⁰⁵ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2004.

¹⁰⁶ 2022/0424(COD), 2022/0425(COD)

¹⁰⁷ European Commission, 2022b; Desku, 2022.

¹⁰⁸ Directive (EU) 2016/681, Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2016b.

¹⁰⁹ Desku, 2022.

¹¹⁰ Andreeva, 2023.

¹¹¹ Regulation (EU) 2018/1240, Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2018b.

¹¹² Ibid., Europa.eu. (n.d.).

¹¹³ Regulation (EU) 2017/2225 and Regulation (EU) 2017/2226, Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2017a and 2017b.

¹¹⁴ The index, middle finger, ring finger and little finger from the right hand [Art. 3(16)].

¹¹⁵ In accordance with Regulation (EU) 2017/2226, specifically Rec.(21), Art. 14, 16 to 19 and 23 of Chapter II and Chapter III.

overstayers and cases of document and identity fraud, whereas Regulation 2017/2226 provides the legal basis for the collection of biometrics in border management, due to (1) their reliability in identifying irregular migrants without (valid) travel documents, and (2) their reliability in matching entry/exit data of bona fide travellers, by combining fingerprints and facial images for maximum accuracy.¹¹⁶

The launches of EES and ETIAS are interdependent. It is currently foreseen that ETIAS will become operational in Spring 2025, a few months after the introduction of the EES, which is expected to launch in Autumn 2024. ETIAS will be subject to a six-month transition period, followed by a six-month grace period.¹¹⁷ The EES and ETIAS are part of a larger framework for **database interoperability** in the areas of internal security and border management.¹¹⁸ Interoperability involves a re-purposing of some databases such as SIS, VIS and Eurodac, providing wider access to the data therein to a wider range of authorities, as well as setting up new databases (EES, ETIAS)¹¹⁹ and several new functionalities:

- A European search portal (ESP), acting as a one-stop shop, enabling simultaneous queries of all Justice and Home Affairs (JHA) information systems and seamless retrieval of necessary information for competent authorities,
- A Common identity repository (CIR), a shared storage for biographical and biometric data of TCNs from VIS, EES and ETIAS,
- A Multiple-identity detector (MID) for cross-checking identity data across various information systems, enabling the detection of multiple identities linked to the same biometric data,
- A shared Biometric Matching Service (sBMS) that will enable the querying and comparison of biometric data from various internal security and border management systems.¹²⁰

Compatibility with the newly set up interoperability systems will be considered in future iterations of the impact assessment for the EINSTEIN applications.

Finally, **the EU Police Cooperation Code** is a package of three legislative acts proposed by the European Commission in December 2021 intended to enhance and spearhead cross-border law enforcement cooperation within the EU, while reforming some information exchange practices.

- Recommendation (EU) 2022/915¹²¹ on operational police cooperation is aimed to strengthen operational cooperation between law enforcement across borders and make it more effective by establishing common standards for officers in joint operations, border areas, during hot pursuit involving multiple LEAs, as well as on more controversial topics such as surveillance and monitoring irregular migration.
- Directive (EU) 2023/977¹²² on the exchange of information between EU LEAs, sets out new rules for information exchange, including an obligation for EU MS to establish a Single Point of Contact (SPOC) responsible for coordinating and facilitating exchanges, by using SIENA. In urgent cases, the information requested should be made available within 8 hours (if directly available to the SPOC) and within 3 days (if the SPOC can obtain it from public authorities or private parties). For all other requests, the information should be made available within 7 days. An EU MS can refuse a request for information; however, it needs to provide a specific and narrow justification. Finally, Europol will be involved in information exchange, inasmuch as it is empowered under Regulation (EU) 2016/794.¹²³

¹¹⁶ Rec(20), also European Commission, (n.d.).

¹¹⁷ European Commission, (n.d.).

¹¹⁸ Regulation (EU) 2019/817 and Regulation (EU) 2019/818, Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2019a and 2019b.

¹¹⁹ The interoperability framework also mandates the development of ECRIS-TCN, a decentralised database on criminal records within the EU.

¹²⁰ eu-LISA, 2022b.

¹²¹ Council of the EU, 2022.

¹²² Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2023.

¹²³ Ibid.

- Regulation (EU) 2024/982¹²⁴ on the automated search and exchange of data for police cooperation (Prüm II regulation) brings about a revision of the Prüm framework, which allows EU LEAs to exchange DNA, fingerprint and vehicle registration data when investigating a crime scene. Prüm II adds more categories of data exchange, including facial images of suspects and convicted criminals and police records. Data collection is only authorised for crime prevention, detection, or investigation. For faster access during criminal investigations, two central routers, the Prüm II router and the European Police Records Index System (EPRIS) will be established, while the new framework also allows Europol access to national databases held by EU countries and vice versa to check third-country-sourced biometric data automatically.¹²⁵ Finally, EU LEAs need to assure that there is a follow-up within 48 hours of a confirmed match on biometric data through the exchange of identification data.

The following chapter will assess the EINSTEIN solutions for potential ELSI at component and application levels, respectively.

¹²⁴ Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2024a.

¹²⁵ Clasen, 2024.

4 ELSI Impact Assessment

This chapter assesses the potential impacts of the EINSTEIN solutions in relation to ELSI. Impacts are assessed both by potential risk, with recommendations for mitigating/preventative actions, and potential opportunity, with recommendations for enabling/enhancing actions. The Impact Assessment is done at two levels, first by component level, and then by Application level.

4.1 Component level

This level of analysis looks at the component technologies that will be integrated to produce the EINSTEIN applications. Three component technologies have been identified:

- Biometrics technologies
- Artificial Intelligence (AI) and algorithms
- Self-Service Technologies (SST)

The separation of components provides an analytical framework to better understand how the components are integrated into the EINSTEIN Applications. This separation is artificial and intended to aid ease of presentation and understanding. In reality the ELSI of biometrics, AI, and SST are overlapping and determined in relation to one another. ELSI findings from five previous research projects (D4FLY; iMARS; SMILE; PERSONA; and PROTECT)¹²⁶, in addition to a review of white and grey literature, form the basis of the component level analysis. As the component level is where the majority of the algorithm development for biometric verification, MAD, and PAD will take place, the mitigation/prevention of ELSI risks at this stage is of particular importance. Failure to take into account risks identified at component level could result in these risks being compounded at the Application level, increasing the challenges of mitigation/prevention. In particular the data processing, system security and the principles of legality, necessity, and proportionality are key when assessing ELSI risks. The EDPS describes the principles of proportionality and necessity as follows:

***Proportionality** is a general principle of EU law. It restricts authorities in the exercise of their powers by requiring them to strike a balance between the means used and the intended aim. In the context of fundamental rights, such as the right to the protection of personal data, proportionality is key for any limitation on these rights. More specifically, proportionality requires that advantages due to limiting the right are not outweighed by the disadvantages to exercise the right. In other words, the limitation on the right must be justified. Safeguards accompanying a measure can support the justification of a measure. A precondition is that the measure is adequate to achieve the envisaged objective. In addition, when assessing the processing of personal data, proportionality requires that only that personal data which is adequate and relevant for the purposes of the processing is collected and processed.*

***Necessity** is a fundamental principle when assessing the restriction of fundamental rights ... the limiting of the fundamental right to the protection of personal data must be strictly necessary. Necessity shall be justified on the basis of objective evidence and is the first step before assessing the proportionality of the limitation. Necessity is also fundamental when assessing the lawfulness of the processing of personal data. The processing operations, the categories of data processed and the duration the data are kept shall be necessary for the purpose of the processing.*

Article 7 of the ECHR and Article 49 of the EU CFR address the principle of legality, whereby:

- No one shall be held guilty of any criminal act on account of any act or omission which did not constitute a criminal offence under national law or international law at the time when it was committed. Nor shall a heavier penalty be imposed than the one that was applicable at the time that the criminal offence was

¹²⁶ Outputs from these projects are undergoing further development as part of EINSTEIN in order to mature their TRL.

committed. If subsequent, to the commission of a criminal offence, the law provides for a lighter penalty, that shall be applicable.

According to the Equality and Human and Rights Commission the principle of legality, ensures that an individual cannot be charged with a criminal offence for an action that is not a crime when it was committed. As a consequence, public authorities must clearly explain what counts a criminal offence so you know when you are breaking the law. In addition to the above principles, the accessibility and foreseeability of safeguards must be considered, as the practical application of legal protections is subject to continuous interpretation and review.

The identification of ELSI opportunities at component level will also support their exploitation at Application level. The IA aims to not only support the development of technologies that will comply with minimum standards for fundamental rights, but seeks to promote and fulfil these rights to their fullest. The integration of these components into the work processes of WP4 and WP5 will be assessed at Application level under Section 4.2.

4.1.1 Biometrics

Biometric technologies are central to contemporary identity management processes, however there is a need for further research to better exploit the value of biometric solutions in this domain.¹²⁷ At the same time, research has highlighted the complex relationship between the use of biometric technologies and potential risks for ELSI. Biometric technologies produce and process biometric data. As per the GDPR (Art 4) and LED (Art 3), biometric data is defined as,

Personal data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person, such as facial images or dactyloscopic data.

The processing of biometric data relates to key rights enshrined and protected under EU law (see Chapter 3). Biometric data are classified as special category personal data and are subject to extensive protections, as the processing of biometrics is understood as a serious interference with fundamental rights.

Multiple biometric technologies have been developed to process different biometric modalities (fingerprint, iris, face, etc.). Increasingly these technologies are combined to provide multimodal biometric solutions. A recent report on the ethical aspects of biometric recognition has noted that while the use of multimodal biometrics “can minimise dangers of fraud and help overcome difficulties caused by poor data quality or missing data, [they can] also increase ethical concerns, as they enable more efficient public surveillance and can be used for the creation of elaborate profiles”.¹²⁸

It must also be noted that biometric technologies rely on biometric matching processes to produce a probabilistic result (i.e. the confidence score). This result is impacted by a number of external factors such as camera resolution, low lighting, bias, spoofing, etc. and should, therefore, not be treated as definitive.¹²⁹ Pesch and Boehm¹³⁰ have argued that “for probabilistic data to be accurate, their probabilistic nature must be apparent from the data. To be processed lawfully, data must furthermore be based on a probabilistic method that is sufficiently reliable and that leads to reasonable results”. This issue is particularly important in relation to the application of biometric technologies for emotion recognition and behaviour detection where the relationship between the data captured and processed by the biometric technologies and the result produced is far more tenuous.¹³¹ The maturation of these novel biometric technologies through development and testing requires careful assessment.

The EINSTEIN Application will incorporate the use of biometric technologies in the following ways:

- Application 1, Online ID Issuing – facial image processing of EU citizen applying for renewal of ID.

¹²⁷ Frontex, 2022.

¹²⁸ Wendehorst and Duller, 2021, p. 14. Author’s additions in parentheses.

¹²⁹ EDPB, 2023, p. 13.

¹³⁰ Pesch and Boehm, 2023, p.32.

¹³¹ See Wendehorst and Duller, 2021.

- Application 2, Mobile document and identity check – facial image of member of the general public processed for fraud detection.
- Application 3, Document authentication – facial images and fingerprints are **not** processed for identification purpose, but to check for potential tampering of documents as part of immigration processing.
- Application 4, Pre-registration for border crossing – facial image is processed as part of the pre-registration process and confirmed at the border crossing point.
- Application 5, EES kiosk with advanced fraud detection – both facial image and fingerprints are processed as part of the EES requirements.
- Application 6, Fast track for enrolled travellers – facial image and iris of pre-enrolled travellers processed as part of border crossing processing.

Given the crucial role (digital) identity management plays in our ability to access public and private services, the impacts of biometric based identity management solutions must be carefully considered. Tables 2 and 3 below outline the ELSI risks and opportunities associated with biometric technologies, along with supporting actions for mitigation and enhancement, respectively.

Table 2: ELSI Risks: Biometric Technologies

ELSI No.	Potential Risk	Suggested Actions to Mitigate/Prevent
1	<p>Failure to respect fundamental rights. This includes: Human dignity; right to integrity; prohibition of inhuman and degrading treatment; non-discrimination; right to asylum; non-refoulement; right of children; right of elderly; rights of people with disabilities; privacy; data protection.</p>	<p>The design and development of the EINSTEIN solutions must seek to protect and promote these fundamental rights. If any of these rights are to be restricted then it must:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be provided for by law, • Respect the essence of the right, • Be necessary and proportionate, • Meet the objectives of general interest to the Union or the need to protect the rights and freedoms of others. <p>Of particular importance here is the rights of the child, as there are ongoing initiatives to lower the age threshold for SST use.¹³²</p>
2	<p>Objectification of the body. Biometrics are intimately linked to the body, the use of biometric solutions is argued to reduce the integrity of bodily relations to objects.</p>	<p>To reduce the risks of objectifying the body:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the cultural and social norms that guide the context of application. • Aim to develop technologies that process less intrusive biometrics. • Assess the impacts of the biometric technology in accordance with the principles of necessity and proportionality.
3	<p>Secondary information revealed. Unexpected personal data, especially health data, could be communicated through the capture of different biometrics.</p>	<p>To reduce the risks of revealing secondary information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is no intention to collect secondary data, such as health data. However, developers and operators should be aware of this risk and measures should be put in place to deal with this appropriately. This is especially important as issues of health are increasingly intersecting with the control of migration and movement.
4	<p>Enrolment bias. The enrolment process is biased against different categories of persons, resulting in discrimination. Particular attention should be paid to potential biases against the following:</p>	<p>To reduce the risks of enrolment bias:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Train the enrolment system on a diverse data set. • Audit system quality for performance.

¹³² For example eu-LISA, 2022b.e, the UK has reduced the age to 10.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Race • Colour • Ethnic or social origin • Genetic features • Religion or belief • Membership of a national minority • Birth • Disability • Age 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Train operators to be aware of potential bias. • Ensure operators are fully informed on any environmental conditions that might restrict use. • Ensure operators are fully informed on any boundary conditions that might restrict use. • Test the enrolment process for optimum set-up and ensure equipment is properly maintained. • Provide alternative means for identity management, in cases where the biometric cannot be captured.
<p>5 Authentication/verification failure. The individual could undergo a significant change to their biometric between the time of enrolment and verification, thereby excluding them from the verification process.</p>	<p>To reduce the risks of authentication/verification failure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use multi-modal, for fall-back biometric verification. • Provide alternative means of authentication/verification, i.e. manual check. • Improve quality of capture threshold for aging.
<p>6 Risk of discrimination. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender • Accessibility • Ethnicity • Religion 	<p>To reduce the risks of discrimination:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the technical development for any limitations that could lead to discrimination. • Consider disabilities and problems for use, e.g. absence or unusable physical body parts; inability to present the required biometric characteristic under particular conditions of operation; inability to access, or difficulty with physical access to the biometric sensor or user terminal, etc. • Provide alternative methods in case of inability to present the required biometric characteristics. • Re-enrol data subjects in case of failure of verification systems.
<p>7 Abuse of data processing. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unauthorised access. • Unlawful processing. • Processed contrary to purpose specifications. • Data minimisation not implemented. • Storage limitation - failure to delete/unlawful retention. 	<p>To reduce risks to data processing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement measures to control access. • Maintain accurate and complete record of logging activities. • Ensure the proper legal bases is identified and satisfied before processing. • Only data that are adequate, relevant, and not excessive in relation to the purpose shall be processed. • Implement data retention and deletion policies.

<p>8 Integrity and confidentiality. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data breaches • Failure to ensure system security 	<p>To reduce risks to integrity and confidentiality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement data protection by-design and by-default measures, including biometric templates (complaint with industry standards and best practices), encryption, anonymisation, partitioning, access controls, traceability, anti-spoofing measures. • Implement data security measures, including operating security, hardware security, back-ups, assess risks of centralised storage versus personal device, implement automated data erasure mechanisms. • Implement supporting organisational policies addressing personnel management, monitoring and management of incidents and breaches, third party relations.
<p>9 Loss of biometric data. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accidental loss, destruction or damage to the biometric data. 	<p>To reduce the risk of loss of biometric data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimise the biometric data collected and implement a secure storage system with a strict time for retention. • Ensure all personal data including biometric data are stored and backed-up in a secure environment. • Ensure protocols for the storage and handling of biometric information are in place. • Ensure contingency plans are in place to address security breaches. • See also recommended actions for Integrity and Confidentiality.
<p>10 Improper management of data processing relations. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outsourcing to external parties (processors and sub-processors). • 3rd party access to biometric data. 	<p>To reduce the risks of improper management of data processing relations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The outsourcing of data processing relations must be managed in accordance with GDPR (Art 28 & 29). • Adhere to the standard contractual clauses between controllers and processors, established by the European Commission.¹³³ • Audit third party relations, including suppliers and integrators for potential risk and vulnerabilities.
<p>11 Improper transfer/Sharing of personal data. This includes but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transfer of data to other public authorities, within the EU and EEA. • Transfer of personal data to third countries, outside the EU and EEA. 	<p>To reduce the risks of improper transfer/sharing of personal data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure compliance with the relevant legal basis for the transfer/sharing of data.

¹³³ Commission Implementing Decision (EU)2021/915.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure only the relevant personal data is shared. • Ensure the quality and accuracy of the data shared. • Ensure the personal data is entered in the correct databases.
<p>12 Poor data quality. This includes but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enrolment issues. • Improper formatting. • Incorrect/inaccurate information. 	<p>To reduce the risks of poor data quality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement data accuracy monitoring and checks. • Audit for compliance with relevant biometric quality standards. • Maintain an open and flexible research process to review and incorporate ongoing developments in this area (see for example the roadmap for standardisation for data quality).
<p>13 Low system accuracy. This can result in either false negatives (the matching process fails to match an individual to their own identity) and/or false positives (the matching process fails to capture a MAD or PAD). False negatives can have a range of impacts, including deterring future use, creating an improper basis for conducting additional checks, and categorising individuals as higher risk. Once produced, the impacts of false negatives are hard to undo, as it difficult to demonstrate how the mistake has occurred, resulting in serious impacts to the individual's life and fundamental right to free movement and right to liberty. Equally, in the case of false positives the risk to society is potentially high as they may have malintent. The consequences of a false positive are serious, as once a biometric has been compromised, a new biometric cannot simply be issued.</p>	<p>To reduce the risks of false negatives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement data quality measures. • Train operators on the probabilistic nature of results. • Implement provisions for the right to redress. • Implement provisions for the right to rectification and erasure. • Implement provisions on the right to information. <p>To reduce the risk of false positives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement anti-spoofing measures, including system security and detection of spoofing attempts. • Notify data subjects of violations and recommend suitable preventive controls.
<p>14 Accountability. The accountability principle requires that the data controller takes responsibility for what is done with personal data and is able to demonstrate compliance with data protection principles.</p>	<p>To reduce the risks to accountability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The data controller shall be accountable for, and able to demonstrate compliance with, the necessary data protection principles and security measures. • Implement an accountability framework that actively engages the management of common accountability issues. See for example, the Accountability Tracker developed by the UK Information Commissioner's Office.
<p>15 Failure to support the right of access. This includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to comply with Article 15, GDPR. • Failure to comply with Article 14, LED. • Failure to comply with Article 17, LED. 	<p>To reduce the risks to the right of access:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement measures to comply with data subject right of access, unless restricted for by law. • Implement processes for review of data access requests.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide clear details on how to perform a right of access request and designate a point of contact for right of access request. • Provide users with the capacity to access and download user information proportionate to security requirements.
<p>16 Failure to support right to redress. This includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to comply with Article 82, GDPR. • Failure to comply with Recitals 146 and 147, GDPR. • Failure to comply with Article 36, LED. 	<p>To reduce the risks to right to redress:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comply with the necessary data processing laws and regulations.
<p>17 Failure to support right to data portability. This includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to comply with Article 20, GDPR. 	<p>To reduce the risks to right to data portability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As several of the Applications are used at the discretion of the user, they must comply with data portability. This requires that personal data is stored in a manner that is structured, common used and machine readable, and can be easily transmitted. • Biometric templates have been excluded from the right to data portability, to prevent function creep.
<p>18 Failure to support the right to information. This includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to comply with Article 12, GDPR. • Failure to comply with Article 13, GDPR. • Failure to comply with Article 14, GDPR. • Failure to comply with Article 12, LED. • Failure to comply with Article 13, LED. • Failure to comply with Article 24, LED. 	<p>To reduce the risks to right to information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide supporting information and signage on the biometric technology. • Outline and make accessible the terms & conditions of use/confidentiality. • Use legible and easy to understand terms. • Provide details of the data processing purposes. • Provide point of contact details for the data controller and processor. • Provide point of contact details for confidentiality issues. • Provide details on any access to/communication of identifiers to third parties. • Provide details on plans to use information to improve system performance. • Use default 'opt-out' function for any non/mandated processing. • Present the user's rights. • Provide information on the secure data storage method. • Provide information on any changes to data collected, purpose and confidentiality clauses.

<p>19 Failure to support right to rectification and erasure. This includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to comply with Article 16, GDPR. • Failure to comply with Article 17, GDPR. • Failure to comply with Article 5, LED. • Failure to comply with Article 13, LED. • Failure to comply with Article 14, LED. • Failure to comply with Article 16, LED. • Failure to comply with Article 24, LED. • Failure to comply with Article 25, LED. • Failure to comply with Article 47, LED. 	<p>To reduce the risks to right to rectification and erasure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement data quality controls. • Comply with data retention and deletion periods, unless restricted by law. • Ensure the proper legal basis for data processing (beyond consent).
<p>20 Transparency, trust, and acceptance. This refers to the potential risks biometric technologies may pose to societal relations. This includes, but is not limited, to issues of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public acceptance of use. • Expectations and norms of use. • Trust in public authorities. • Trust in private technology developers. 	<p>To reduce the risks to transparency, trust, and acceptance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider social and cultural differences in the user acceptance of biometric technologies for identity management. • Consider social and cultural differences in expectations relating to the use of biometric technologies by border control and law enforcement. • Consider social and cultural differences on the degree of trust between the public and public authorities (this can lead both to a desire for more automation to reduce the likelihood of human error and discrimination, or less automation as data may be processed unlawfully). • Ensuring data processing is transparent (see right to information).
<p>21 Function creep. This includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The risk of data being used against their original purposes. 	<p>To reduce the risk of function creep:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data must not be processed contrary to the principle of purpose limitation.
<p>22 Chilling effect. This refers to the unjustified and over-use of biometric solutions for surveillance purposes, whereby individuals may feel they cannot access their legal rights due to fear of sanction or retribution. This creates long-term damage to the trust between the public and states.</p>	<p>To reduce the risk of chilling effects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The deployment of biometric technologies must meet the threshold tests for the principles of proportionality and necessity.
<p>23 Potential for invasive surveillance. This refers to the fact that biometric technologies are software based, and may be operating without the users' knowledge and biometric data is collected unknowingly from individuals.</p>	<p>To reduce the risk of invasive surveillance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users must be properly informed that biometric technologies are in used, expect where provided for by law. • Users must be provided with the ability to opt-out, without repercussion, except where provided for by law.

<p>24 Incompatible regulatory context. Current technical capabilities are not always aligned to regulatory context. The legal deployment of a biometric technologies must be guided by the regulatory constraints and not the capabilities of the technology. At the same time the regulatory environment is not static and biometric technologies must be developed in ways which are future proofed.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do not process personal data without the users' knowledge and consent, except where provided for by law. <p>To reduce the risk of incompatible regulatory context:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure compliance with the current regulatory landscape in the business use case development. Where the business use case limits the deployment of the technical solution, implement alternative measures that will allow for an equitable experience. For example, automated border control solutions are not accessible to single parents travelling with children alone, as additional checks are required. To achieve a similar travel experience, ensure that manual checks are easily accessible, convenient and easy to use. This allows for an equitable travel experience, while still ensuring the safety and security of the child. Implement a flexible design and development process that can respond to changes in the regulatory environment.
<p>25 Incompatible operating environment. The introduction of new technologies into the operating environment may require new ways of working. Incompatibility between the operating environment and the implementation of the solution may pose potential risks. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Worker fatigue (mental and physical). Time pressures. Contradictory requirements (passenger flow, degree of check). Low market uptake. Low rates of implementation and use. 	<p>To reduce the risk of incompatible operating environment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop the solution in co-creation with the customer to ensure it is fit for purpose and designed for operational use.
<p>26 Immature technologies. Biometric technologies for emotion detection and abnormal behaviour detection are a developing field of research. The results produced under these biometrics technologies are not as accurate as more established biometric technologies such as fingerprint and facial image.</p>	<p>To reduce the risk of immature technologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carry out further research to mature this area of biometric solutions. Inform operators of the current limitation of these technologies and what this means for the reliability of the results.

Table 3: ELSI Opportunities: Biometric Technologies

ELSI No.	Potential Opportunity	Suggested Actions to Enable/Improve
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<p>1 Improved confidence in identity verification/authentication. The introduction of biometric technologies can offer systematic and reliable assessment of identities.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rigorously test and validate the technologies for potential inaccuracies, bias, and False Rejection Rate (FRR) and False Acceptance Rate (FAR). • Train operators on the correct use and interpretation of the results. • Create a secure system that increases user trust and uptake.
<p>2 Rationalisation of human resources. The introduction of biometric technologies can free up operators to focus on cases that require more thorough checks.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rigorously test and validate the technologies for potential inaccuracies, bias, and FRR and FAR. • Train operators on the correct use and interpretation of the results. • Create a secure system that increases user trust and uptake.
<p>3 Upskilling. The introduction of biometric technologies provides operators with an opportunity for upskilling in a digital economy.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The use of these technologies can help to train operators in detecting fraud. Provide training and upskilling to operators to support these capabilities. • Provide training to users of self-service technologies.
<p>4 Reduces the need for multiple passwords. The introduction of biometric technologies, can support identity management by providing stable identifier without the use of multiple passwords.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplified UI that is easy to understand and use. • A secure system that does not rely on the user to create, store and remember multiple complex passwords.
<p>5 Contactless identity management. The introduction of biometric technologies can support contactless identity management by reducing physical touchpoints and human interaction.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many biometric technologies support contactless biometric enrolment, capture, and comparison. This can add value in terms of hygiene, bodily autonomy and integrity and respect for religion.
<p>6 Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs). The introduction of biometric technologies can support the maturation of PETs.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploit opportunities for the inclusion of PET in the development of the EINSTEIN solutions. • Integrate cutting edge research on PET to further mature these technologies and aid their progression to market.
<p>7 Preventing serious organised crime. The introduction of biometric technologies can aid the detection and prevention of fraud.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop robust solutions that reduce the risk of identity theft. • Develop high quality solutions, that are compliant with ELSI, to improve uptake and adoption post project.

4.1.2 Artificial Intelligence and Algorithms

As with biometric technologies, AI systems are increasingly central to contemporary identity management processes. The role of AI systems in (digital) identity management is expanding. Research has highlighted the complex relationship between the use of AI systems and potential risks for ELSI, particularly in the fields of border management and law enforcement.¹³⁴ As per the March 2024 adopted text for the AI act, an AI system is defined as:¹³⁵

a machine-based system designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy, that may exhibit adaptiveness after deployment and that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments.

An algorithm can be described as “a set of instructions or steps used to solve a problem (e.g., it does not include the data). The algorithm can be abstract and implemented in different programming languages and software libraries”.¹³⁶ Algorithms can be categorised according to their learning style, supervised, semi-supervised, unsupervised, and generally rely on three techniques for learning: machine learning, deep learning, and natural language processing. EINSTEIN will develop algorithms using machine learning and deep learning, these will be trained in an unsupervised/weakly supervised format. EINSTEIN will deploy three types of algorithms:

- Algorithms for Morphing Attack Detection (MAD);
- Algorithms for Presentation Attack Detection (PAD);
- Algorithms for biometric quality assessment.

The Algorithms are being sourced either as part of prior project work to be developed further under EINSTEIN, or as open source materials (e.g BIS OFIQ). The algorithms developed within EINSTEIN will be evaluated against state-of-the-art requirements, using the Bologna Online Evaluation Platform for benchmarking.¹³⁷

The use of AI systems for border management and law enforcement has been classified as high risk (as per the AIA classification), and the potential risks associated with AI systems to ELSI must be carefully considered. Of particular importance here is the mitigation of risks related to bias. This includes algorithmic bias, sampling bias, automation bias, aggregation bias and bias as a result of data preparation and quality issues. The ethical guidelines for trustworthy AI put forward by the EU HLEG (High Level Expert Group) on Artificial Intelligence¹³⁸ should serve as a starting point for any AI development:¹³⁹

- Human agency and oversight

Requires that AI systems support human agency and decision-making, rather than replacing them. Human agency entails providing safeguards to avoid that AI systems can negatively affect or influence human decision-making. AI systems must be evaluated for whether they tend to foster over-reliance on the system instead of on human judgment, while the users must be informed that they are interacting with an AI system or the result of an AI system’s decision-making. Human oversight then requires that AI systems are designed with features allowing human supervision of processes and algorithms, such as human-in-the-loop (HITL), human-on-the-loop (HOTL), or human-in command (HIC) approaches.

¹³⁴ See González Fuster, 2020.

¹³⁵ Available online at: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2024-0138_EN.pdf

¹³⁶ Estévez Almenzar et al., 2022, p. 10

¹³⁷ For more information, see: <https://biolab.csr.unibo.it/fvcongoing/UI/Form/Home.aspx>

¹³⁸ EU High Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019a.

¹³⁹ For further details on the specifics of these recommendations, see: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

The EINSTEIN project is funded by the European Union (EU) under G.A. no. 101121280 and UKRI Funding Service under IFS reference 10093453. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect the views of the EU/Executive Agency or UKRI. Neither the EU nor the granting authority nor UKRI can be held responsible for them.

- Technical robustness and safety

Requires that AI components be dependable and resilient, including to external interference. AI systems must be robust with respect to changes in their operating environment or the presence of other agents (human or artificial) that may interact with the system in an adversarial manner. From a security perspective, it is crucial that AI systems be protected from vulnerabilities that could be exploited by adversarial actors, and that they are resilient to potential cyberattacks. This principle also enshrines accuracy, requiring that AI systems be continuously assessed for the accuracy of their predictions, which are expected to be reliable and reproducible.

- Privacy and data governance

This requirement recognises that privacy is closely linked to the principle of prevention of harm, a fundamental right particularly affected by AI systems. The requirement for the protection of Personal Data is enshrined in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU (CFR Art. 8), including the right to the integrity of the person (CFR Art. 3). It also aims at ensuring equality and fundamental freedoms as personal data can be used for discriminatory purposes or in unauthorised surveillance practices. Prevention of harm to privacy necessitates adequate data governance, which entails a data management plan is implemented to ensure the quality and integrity of the data used, the AI component's access to protocols and the capability to process data in a manner that protects privacy, in accordance with the GDPR/LED.

- Transparency

Requires that the purposes, outputs and operation of AI systems are understandable and explainable to their human users, including the data and systems involved therein. The AI HLEG suggests a three-fold approach to transparency which includes the sub-requirements of traceability, explainability, and communication. Traceability entails that the datasets and processes involved in the AI system's decision are documented to ensure transparency, by allowing users to trace them. Explainability refers to the technical and human decision-making of AI systems, requiring that the decisions made can be understood and explained, by incorporating certain design choices, such as logging. Communication refers to the necessity for AI systems to inform their human users that they are interacting with an AI component, in order to avoid misinterpretation of results, or overreliance on these due to automation bias (i.e. an exaggerated trust in the output of technological solutions).

- Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

Under this requirement, AI systems must ensure that inclusion and diversity are guaranteed throughout the system's lifecycle. This entails an avoidance of unfair bias, which may be due to the datasets or algorithms applied, or else due to inherent bias of the humans and entities involved in the design process. This in turn requires safeguards such as explainability of the results and human oversight processes in order to ensure the fairness of the system's outputs. To fulfil the requirement, AI HLEG also recommends providing equal access to a large variety of social groups to AI systems through inclusive design, beyond the foreseen end-users.

- Societal and environmental wellbeing

Society, other sentient beings, and the environment should be considered stakeholders in AI systems' lifecycle, necessitating a societally responsible and environmentally sustainable approach to their development and operation. Thereby resource usage and energy consumption should be considered in the design and deployment of AI systems and their supply chain to ensure they are prudent in their energy usage. Furthermore, the AI system's social impact and effects on democracy should be considered in the design process, as they can be expected to affect social relationships and skills, while their effects on political decision-making and electoral processes should be carefully considered.

- Accountability

Requires that AI systems are accountable for their outputs, both before and after deployment. This entails auditability of algorithms, datasets and system design to internal and external auditors to increase the transparency of the systems. It further requires minimising and reporting on negative impacts and responding to the consequences of those, by identifying and documenting these, including through the use of impact assessments. If and when such negative impacts occur, the AI HLEG mandates those responsible for the AI systems mechanisms

address these adequately, and overall developers are expected to avoid trade-offs resulting in inadequate adherence to the ethical and legal principles applicable to the operation of AI systems.

Potential risks and recommendations for mitigation/prevention for AI and algorithms have been summarised from the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI for self-assessment (ALTAI)¹⁴⁰, as outlined below. In addition, a table of opportunities has been developed to enable/enhance the benefits AI and algorithms offer to digital identity management.

¹⁴⁰ EU High Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b.

Table 4: ELSI Risks: AI and Algorithms

ELSI No.	Potential Risk	Suggested Actions to Mitigate/Prevent
1	Does the AI system potentially negatively discriminate against people on the basis of any of the following grounds (non-exhaustively): sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation?	To reduce the risk of negative discrimination: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Put in place processes to test and monitor for potential negative discrimination (bias) during the development, deployment and use phases of the AI system. Put in place processes to address and rectify for potential negative discrimination (bias) in the AI system.
2	Failure to respect the rights of the child.	To reduce risks to the rights of the child: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Put in place processes to ensure child protection and taking the child's best interests into account. Put in place processes to address and rectify for potential harm to children by the AI system. Put in place processes to test and monitor for potential harm to children during the development, deployment and use phases of the AI system.
3	Failure to protect personal data relating to individuals in line with GDPR.	To reduce the risk of GDPR non-compliance: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Put in place processes to assess in detail the need for a data protection impact assessment, including an assessment of the necessity and proportionality of the processing operations in relation to their purpose, with respect to the development, deployment and use phases of the AI system Put in place measures envisaged to address the risks, including safeguards, security measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data with respect to the development, deployment and use phases of the AI system Review the section on Privacy and Data Governance in this Assessment List, and available guidance from the European Data Protection Supervisor.

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<p>4 Failure to respect the freedom of expression and information and/or freedom of assembly and association.</p>	<p>To reduce risks to freedom of expression and information and/or freedom of assembly and association:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Put in place processes to test and monitor for potential infringement on freedom of expression and information, and/or freedom of assembly and association, during the development, deployment and use phases of the AI system. • Put in place processes to address and rectify for potential infringement on freedom of expression and information, and/or freedom of assembly and association, in the AI system.
<p>5 Failure to support human agency and autonomy. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confusion on whether a decision/content/advice/outcome is the result of an algorithmic decision. • Failure to inform users they are interacting with an AI system. • Failure to put in place procedures that prevent over-reliance on the AI system. • Failure to put in place procedures that prevent the AI system from interfering with user’s decision-making processes. • Failure to put in place procedures that minimise the risk of addiction; mitigate the risk of manipulation; and deal with potential consequences of disproportionate attachment to the AI system. 	<p>To reduce risks to human agency and autonomy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarify and communicate the decision-making process to the relevant parties. • Inform users when and how they are interacting with an AI system. • Integrate bright design patterns that monitor and inform the user of their reliance on AI systems. • Integrate bright design patters that support the decision-making capacity and capability of the user. • Integrate bright design patterns for user experience.
<p>6 Failure to provide human oversight. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of oversight (e.g. human-in-the-loop; human-on-the-loop; human-in-command). • Failure to provide specific training on how to exercise oversight. • Failure to establish detection and response mechanisms for undesirable adverse effects of the AI system on the user. • Failure to implement a ‘stop’ button/procedure to safely abort an operation when needed. • Failure to implement oversight and control mechanisms to reflect the self-learning or autonomous nature of the AI system. 	<p>To reduce risks to human oversight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure proportionate and meaningful oversight and fail safes are in place. • Provide training on how to exercise oversight, with practical testing and updated frequently. • Define and establish pre-emptive response mechanisms for undesirable adverse effects. • Provide a ‘stop’/‘abort’ function. • Implement oversight and control mechanisms for system learning style.
<p>7 Failure to provide resilience to attack and security. This includes, but is not limited to:</p>	<p>To reduce risks to resilience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the risks to the system and the potential impacts of those risks.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to consider if the AI system could have adversarial, critical or damaging effects (e.g. to human or societal safety) in case of risks or threats such as design or technical faults, defects, outages, attacks, misuse, inappropriate or malicious use. • Failure to achieve cybersecurity certification and/or compliance with necessary security standards. • Failure to assess the vulnerability of the AI system to potential forms of attack. • Failure to consider different types of vulnerabilities and different entry points for attacks. • Failure to put measures in place to ensure the integrity, robustness and overall security of the AI system against potential attacks over its lifecycle. • Failure to sufficiently test the system for potential vulnerabilities and attacks. • Failure to inform the user of the duration of security coverage and updates. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Submit the system to cybersecurity certification. • Assess the vulnerability of the system to various types of attack. • Implement security control measures. • Test security control measures. • Clearly communicate the conditions of the security protection the user. Clearly inform the user of any actions they will need to take to main security. Confirm acknowledgement of this understanding with the user.
<p>8 Failure to provide general safety. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to put in place measures to assess risks, risk metrics and risk levels of the AI system. • Failure to inform users of existing or potential risks. • Failure to identify possible threats to the AI system (design faults, technical faults, environmental threats) and the possible consequences. • Failure to assess the dependency of a critical AI system’s decisions on its stable and reliable behaviour? • Failure to plan fault tolerance. • Failure to develop a mechanism to evaluate when the AI system has been changed to merit a new review of its technical robustness and safety. 	<p>To reduce risks to safety:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the risk of possible malicious use, misuse or inappropriate use system. • Identify possible threats to the system. • Inform users of existing or potential risks and threats. • Define safety criticality levels (e.g. related to human integrity) of the possible consequences of faults or misuse of the AI system. • Align the reliability/testing requirements to the appropriate levels of stability and reliability. • Design fail-safe, e.g. duplicated system or another parallel system (AI-based or ‘conventional’).
<p>9 Failure to support accuracy. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to consider how a low level of accuracy of the AI system result in critical, adversarial or damaging consequences? • Failure to put in place measures to ensure that the data (including training data) used to develop the AI system is up-to-date, of high quality, complete and representative of the environment the system will be deployed in? • Failure to put in place steps to monitor, and document the AI system’s accuracy. 	<p>To reduce risks to accuracy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the level of accuracy and its potential consequences. • Monitor and evaluate the training dataset. • Implement regular monitoring and spot checks to ensure accuracy remain high and consistent. • Communicate the to be expected level of accuracy to the user. Highlight any limitations and potential sign/causes of decrease in accuracy.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to consider whether the AI system's operation can invalidate the data or assumptions it was trained on, and how this might lead to adversarial effects. • Failure to put processes in place to ensure that the level of accuracy of the AI system to be expected by end-users and/or subjects is properly communicated. 	
<p>10 Failure to implement reliability, fall back plans, and reproducibility. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to consider the consequences of low reliability and/or reproducibility. • Failure to put in place verification and validation methods and documentation (e.g. logging) to evaluate and ensure the AI system's reliability and reproducibility. • Failure to define tested failsafe fallback plans to address AI system errors, and put governance procedures in place to trigger them. • Failure to put in place a proper procedure for handling cases where the AI system yields results with a low confidence score. • Is your AI system using (online) continual learning. 	<p>To reduce risks to reliability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Put in place a well-defined process to monitor if the AI system is meeting the intended goals. • Test whether specific contexts or conditions need to be taken into account to ensure reproducibility. • Clearly document and operationalise processes for the testing and verification of the reliability and reproducibility of the AI system. • Consider potential negative consequences from the AI system learning novel or unusual methods to score well on its objective function. • The system will be deployed in closed operating conditions. The training process for development will be compliant with AI Act requirements on transparency. The majority of the training datasets are based either on publicly available datasets or previous research datasets, providing the consortium with control over the design of the sample distribution.
<p>11 Failure to support privacy. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to consider the impact of the AI system on the right to privacy, the right to physical, mental and/or moral integrity and the right to data protection. 	<p>To reduce risks to privacy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish mechanisms to flag issues related to privacy. • Execute a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA).
<p>12 Failure to support data governance. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to know if your AI system is being trained, or was it developed, by using or processing personal data (including special categories of personal data). • Failure to put in place measures to support data governance, some of which are mandatory under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), or a non-European equivalent. • Failure to consider the privacy and data protection implications of the AI system's non-personal training-data or other processed non-personal data. 	<p>To reduce risks to data governance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Execute a DPIA for the whole of the AI system's lifecycle. • Designate a Data Protection Officer (DPO) to be included at an early state in the development, procurement or use phase of the AI system. • Establish oversight mechanisms for data processing (including limiting access to qualified personnel, mechanisms for logging data access and making modifications).

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to align the AI system with relevant standards (e.g. ISO25, IEEE26) or widely adopted protocols for (daily) data management and governance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement measures to achieve privacy-by-design and default (e.g. encryption, pseudonymisation, aggregation, anonymisation). • Follow the principle of data minimisation, in particular for personal data (including special categories of data). • Implement the right to withdraw consent, the right to object and the right to be forgotten into the development of the AI system, unless provided for by law.
<p>13 Failure to support traceability. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to put in place measures that address the traceability of the AI system during its entire lifecycle. 	<p>To reduce risks to traceability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the quality of input data. • Test the ability to trace back which data was used by the AI system to make a certain decision(s) or recommendation(s). • Test the ability to trace back which AI model or rules led to the decision(s) or recommendation(s) of the AI system. • Place measures to continuously assess the quality of the output(s) of the AI system. • Implement and reinforce logging practices.
<p>14 Failure to support explainability. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to explain the decision(s) of the AI system to the users. <p>Explainability covers the development process, operator understanding on decision-making processes, and technical clarity of the decision-making.</p>	<p>To reduce risks to explainability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop system capabilities and functions to support explainable AI, including training, human factors analysis of the UI, technical explainability, clear protocols on the chain of responsibility of users, identify and establish roles and responsibilities of data controller and data processor, automatic (activity) logging on the use of the system, reviewing algorithmic accuracy, auditing. • Continuously survey the users if they understand the decision(s) of the AI system. Identify and address any additional needs to improve explainability.
<p>15 Failure to support communication. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to communicate to users that they are interacting with an AI system instead of a human. 	<p>To reduce risks to communication:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clearly communicate the benefits of the AI system to users.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to establish mechanisms to inform users about the purpose, criteria and limitations of the decision(s) generated by the AI system. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clearly communicate the technical limitations and potential risks of the AI system to users, such as its level of accuracy and/or error rates. • Provide appropriate training material and disclaimers to users on how to adequately use the AI system.
<p>16 Failure to avoid unfair bias. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to establish a strategy or a set of procedures to avoid creating or reinforcing unfair bias in the AI system, both regarding the use of input data as well as for the algorithm design. • Failure to consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and/or subjects in the data. • Failure to ensure a mechanism that allows for the flagging of issues related to bias, discrimination or poor performance of the AI system. • Failure to consider how your definition of fairness is commonly used and implemented in any phase of the process of setting up the AI system. 	<p>To reduce the risk of unfair bias:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test for specific target groups or problematic use cases. • Research and use publicly available technical tools, that are state-of-the-art, to improve your understanding of the data, model and performance. • Assess and put in place processes to test and monitor for potential biases during the entire lifecycle of the AI system. • Did you consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and or subjects in the data. • Put in place educational and awareness initiatives to help AI designers and AI developers be more aware of the possible bias they can inject in designing and developing the AI system. Establish clear steps and ways of communicating on how and to whom such issues can be raised. • Identify the subjects that could potentially be (in)directly affected by the AI system, in addition to the (end-)users and/or subjects. • Consider other possible definitions of fairness. • Consult with the impacted communities about the correct definition of fairness, i.e. representatives of elderly persons or persons with disabilities. • Implement a quantitative analysis or metrics to measure and test the applied definition of fairness. • Establish mechanisms to ensure fairness in your AI system.
<p>17 Failure to promote accessibility and universal design. This includes, but is not limited to:</p>	<p>To reduce risks to accessibility:</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to ensure that the AI system corresponds to the variety of preferences and abilities in society. • Failure assessing whether the AI system's user interface is usable by those with special needs or disabilities or those at risk of exclusion. • Failure to ensure that Universal Design principles are taken into account during every step of the planning and development process, if applicable. • Failure to take the impact of the AI system on the potential end-users and/or subjects into account. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure that information about the AI system, and the AI system's user interface is accessible and usable to users of assistive technologies (such as screen readers). • Consult with end-users or subjects in need for assistive technology during the planning and development phase of the AI system. • Assess whether there could be groups who might be disproportionately affected by the outcomes of the AI system. Take steps to mitigate/reduce these impacts. • Assess the risk of the possible unfairness of the system onto the end-user's or subject's communities.
<p>18 Failure to promote stakeholder participation. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to consider mechanisms to include the participation of the widest range of possible stakeholders in the AI system's design and development. 	<p>To reduce the risk of non-participation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage in co-creation design methods.
<p>19 Failure to address environmental well-being. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to consider potential negative impacts of the AI system on the environment. • Failure to establish, where possible, mechanisms to evaluate the environmental impact of the AI system's development, deployment and/or use (for example, the amount of energy used and carbon emissions). 	<p>To reduce risks to environmental well-being:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the environmental costs of the AI system. • Define measures to reduce the environmental impact of the AI system throughout its lifecycle. • Design applications with lower energy usage.
<p>20 Failure to address impact on work and skills. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to consider if the AI system impact human work and work arrangements. • Failure to adopt measures to ensure that the impacts of the AI system on human work are well understood. • Failure to consider if the AI system create the risk of de-skilling of the workforce. • Failure to promote or require new (digital) skills. 	<p>To reduce risks to work and skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform and consult with impacted workers and their representatives (trade unions, (European) work councils) in advance. • Ensure that workers understand how the AI system operates, which capabilities it has and which it does not have. • Take measures to counteract de-skilling risks. • Provide training opportunities and materials for re- and up-skilling.
<p>21 Failure to address impact on society at large or democracy. This includes, but is not limited to:</p>	<p>To reduce the risks to society or democracy:</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to consider if the AI system have a negative impact on society at large or democracy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the societal impact of the AI system’s use beyond the (end-)user and subject, such as potentially indirectly affected stakeholders or society at large. • Take action to minimize potential societal harm of the AI system. • Take measures that ensure that the AI system does not negatively impact democracy.
<p>22 Failure to implement auditability. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to establish mechanisms that facilitate the AI system’s auditability. • Failure to ensure that the AI system can be audited by independent third parties. 	<p>To reduce risks to auditability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement measures to support the traceability of the development process, e.g. the sourcing of training data and the logging of the AI system’s processes, outcomes, positive and negative impact. • Submit the AI system and its development process to an independent evaluation.
<p>23 Failure to implement risk management. This includes, but is not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure to include any kind of external guidance or third-party auditing processes to oversee ethical concerns and accountability measures. • Failure to organise risk training. • Failure to establish a process to discuss and continuously monitor and assess the AI system's adherence to this Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI). • Failure to establish a process for third parties (e.g. suppliers, end-users, subjects, distributors/vendors or workers) to report potential vulnerabilities, risks or biases in the AI system. • Failure to put redress by design mechanisms in place applications that can adversely affect individuals. 	<p>To strengthen risk management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand auditing beyond the development phase. • Identify the legal frameworks applicable to the AI system. • Establish an AI ethics review board or a similar mechanism to discuss the overall accountability and ethics practices, including potential unclear grey areas. • Identify and document potential conflicts between managing potential ELSI risks and explain the 'trade-off' of decisions made. • Provide appropriate training to those involved in such a process, including on the legal framework applicable to the AI system. • If required, revise the risk management process.

Table 5: ELSI Opportunities: AI and Algorithms

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ELSI No.	Potential Opportunity	Suggested Actions to Enable/Improve
1	Avoid bias by providing a balanced dataset. This refers to the development of diverse dataset to train AI systems and algorithms	Provide a balanced dataset.
2	Discover connections between datapoints in large datasets. This refers the capacity of AI systems and algorithms to identity and detect patterns that are not detectable at human level.	Provide a state-of-the-art AI model that can make reliable connections between datapoints.
3	Reduce workload for officers. This refers to the capacity of AI systems and algorithms to reduce the strain of repetitive and unfulfilling tasks.	Provide training on use of AI system, digital literacy.
4	Sensitising officers to bias. This refers to the opportunity to provide training to operators to deepen their understanding of how AI systems and algorithms work, and the boundary conditions of their use.	Provide training on potential sources of biases, how bias might express itself in the system and how to identity and mitigate bias. Communicate the seriousness of the consequences of bias.
5	Auditability of decision-making. This refers to the implementation of mechanisms to reviewing decision-making processes, and system inputs/outputs they are based on.	Implement and reinforce a culture of diligent logging, auditing, algorithmic assessment, supported by technical accountability.
6	Upskilling. The introduction of AI systems and algorithms can provide operators with an opportunity to upskill in a growing digital economy.	Extensive training and adequate user manuals, taking into account varying levels of digital literacy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The use of these technologies can help to train operators in detecting fraud. Provide training and upskilling to operators. • Provide trainings to user of self-service technologies.
7	Privacy Enhancing Technologies. The introduction of AI systems and algorithms can support the maturation of PETs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploit opportunities for the inclusion of PET in the development of the EINSTEIN solutions. • Integrate cutting edge research on PET to further mature these technologies and aid their progression to market.
8	Preventing serious organised crime. The introduction of AI systems and algorithms can aid the detection and prevention of fraud.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop robust solutions that reduce the risk of identity theft. • Develop high quality solutions, that are compliant with ELSI, to improve uptake and adoption post project.

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4.1.3 Self-Service Technologies

Self-service technologies (SST) are an increasingly common component of identity management processes, particularly for border control, as travellers are encouraged to manage their own journeys under a vision of seamless travel. Meuter et al.¹⁴¹ describe SST as “technological interfaces that enable customers to produce a service independent of direct service employee involvement”. While previously limited to administrative tasks such as checking-in and baggage check, SST are increasingly being developed and trialled as part of the security process.¹⁴² Indeed, the EES regulation formalises the role of SST in identity management processes for European border control. SST are a critical part of the operating infrastructure enabling and supporting the digitalisation of the identity management process.

SST will be used in the EINSTEIN Applications in the following ways:

- Application 1, Online ID Issuing – a member of the public accesses the Application and uploads their ID renewal application in addition to a selfie. This process interfaces with the existing identity renewal checks of the public authority.
- Application 2, Mobile document and identity check – this Application is operated by a member of a public authority and is **not** a SST.
- Application 3, Document authentication – this Application is operated by a member of a public authority and is **not** a SST.
- Application 4, Pre-registration for border crossing – a member of the travelling public will pre-register their details in advance of crossing a border point. This information assessed is potential fraud and forwarded to the border management authority for final confirmation.
- Application 5, EES kiosk with advanced fraud detection – individuals required to evidence their entry and exit of the EU in compliance with requirements set out in Reg (EU) 2017/2226 present their passport to the kiosk. A live image facial capture is performed by the kiosk camera. Both the document and live image are analysed for potential fraud. This process is monitored by a border control agent.
- Application 6, Fast track for enrolled travellers – Using the pre-registration app (Application 4), users will access a contactless biometric corridor to cross the border without stopping. The traveller enters the corridor independently, however the border crossing is supervised by an operator. In cases of a successful verification the traveller is automatically guided to the exit of the corridor area. In cases of a negative verification result the traveller is guided to a border guard booth for further inspection.

The increasing use of SST brings to the fore important ongoing debates around the rights and responsibilities of different users. On the one hand, SST can provide the user with greater control over their own data, in line with SSI models. On the other hand, SST can result in the over responsabilisation of the user, as they must familiarise themselves with the consequences of their choices, and become adept with navigating the many digital platforms and interfaces required to use SST in a meaningful way. This issue has been especially highlighted in relation to how older persons may be restricted in accessing public services due to their simultaneous digitalisation and shift to self-service models.¹⁴³ While focusing on the impacts of digitalisation for older persons, the report also notes the interplay of social and digital inequalities. These matters are further complicated as the consequences of integrating of self-service models into politically sensitive domains such as digital identity management are still being worked out. Royakkers et al.¹⁴⁴ identify 6 social and ethical themes evoked by digitalisation that can help to guide the assessment of SST.

¹⁴¹ Meuter et al., 2000, p. 50.

¹⁴² See PERSONA (2019) for an overview of self-service technologies that have been implemented in support of seamless travel experiences across the globe.

¹⁴³ FRA, 2023.

¹⁴⁴ Royakkers et al., 2018, p. 138.

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Table 6: Ethical and Social Issues for Digitalisation

Theme	Issues
Privacy	Data protection, spatial privacy, mental privacy, Little Brother, pervasive monitoring, transparency.
Autonomy	Freedom of choice, freedom of expression, manipulation, paternalism, controlling influences.
Safety & security	Safety of information, identity fraud, physical and psychological safety.
Balance of power	Unfair competitions, exploitation, relation citizen-government-industry, accountability, control and transparency of algorithms.
Human dignity	Dehumanization, instrumentalization, deskilling (unlearning skills), desocialization.
Justice	Discrimination, exclusion, equal treatment, stigmatization, function creep.

Research addressing the role of SST has often focused on user experience and user interface (UI). This work has been characterised in terms of bright and dark patterns. Kelly and Rubin¹⁴⁵ describe dark patterns as UI “strategies designed to influence users to perform actions or make choices that benefit the service provider”. Examples of dark patterns include: hidden costs, bait and switch, forced continuity, roach motel, misdirection, confirm-shaming, sneak into basket, friend spam, disguised ads, trick questions, FOMO, and price comparison prevention.¹⁴⁶ By contrast, bright patterns are described as antonyms to dark patterns, seeking to prioritise user goals and well-being.

The use of SST in border management and law enforcement raises complex issues regarding the balance of power between SST users and operators, as many activities in this space are mandatory, providing the user with little to no option to decline/opt-out. Ensuring alternative options to SST are in place is critical, as the rights and responsibilities of multiple groups must be balanced. At the same time, previous research has highlighted the potential benefits of SST as they may reduce the impact of human discrimination and bias.¹⁴⁷ And, SST, like many other digitalisation technologies, are argued to support both the rationalisation of resources as the volume of travellers grows, and respond to traveller demands for convenience, speed, and improved travel experiences.

Tables 6 and 7 below outline the ELSI risks and opportunities associated with SST, along with recommendations for mitigation and enhancement, respectively.

¹⁴⁵ Kelly and Rubin, 2024.

¹⁴⁶ For further details, see: <https://www.deceptive.design/types>.

¹⁴⁷ See PERSONA, 2018.

Table 7: ELSI Risks Self-Service Technologies

ELSI No.	Potential Risk	Suggested Actions to Mitigate/Prevent
1	Dark patterns. The development of the SST must avoid design choices that place undue pressure on the user or try to manipulate the user into taking unnecessary actions.	To reduce the risk of dark patterns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop awareness of potential dark patterns by attending to user expectations and values associated with use. • Avoid the use of dark patterns in the design of the SST UI.
2	User literacy. The use of SST relies on high levels of digital literacy and familiarity, as users will need to take control of a number of steps in the digital identity management process, previously carried out by (public) service provider.	To reduce the risk of user literacy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support user literacy with information materials. • Assess the usability of the SST against multiple target groups with varying degrees of technical literacy and familiarity. • Provide access to support staff to guide the user through the process. • Provide access to alternative means to access the service for users unable to use the SST.
3	Insufficient user support. The implementation of SST requires the presence of a sufficient number of staff to assist persons with their use.	To reduce the risk of insufficient user support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the minimum number of personnel required to oversee the user of the SST. • Identify, categorise and troubleshoot the human factors that will require additional support from staff. • Train operators on the how they will be expected to provide these supports.
4	Improper supervision of SST. The use of SST in the context of border management and law enforcement, requires proper supervision to prevent fraud and spoofing attempts.	To reduce the risk of improper supervision of SST: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop metrics to measure and assess thresholds for optimal human/SST supervision.
5	System security. The soon-to-be most ubiquitous SST, in the context of digital identity management, is the mobile smartphone. Smartphones bring together multiple third parties software developers, increasing the opportunity for security vulnerabilities.	To reduces risks to system security: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design the SST to be compliant with all relevant industry standards and best practices for security. • Test the system for security risks and vulnerabilities. • Assess non-closed SST for potential security risks and vulnerabilities. • Regularly view and integrate research on new vulnerabilities.

<p>6 Digital divides and unequal access to service. Services are rarely evenly distributed and accessible to all. Socio-economic status is increasingly becoming a differential factor in how identity management processes are experienced, e.g. priority lanes.</p>	<p>To reduce the risk of digital divides and unequal access to services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider any potential barriers to access, including but not limited to: cost, location, access to internet. • Provide access to alternative means to access the service for users unable to use the SST.
<p>7 Increased user burden of labour. SST require the user to take on the labour cost of tasks previously carried out by the service provider, creating an additional burden on the user.</p>	<p>To reduce the risks of increased user burdens of labour:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop high quality solutions where the costs of user labour is outweighed by the benefits the service provides. • Provide easy access to alternative means to access the service for users unable to use the SST.
<p>8 Choke points. System failures create a potential choke point in service provision. More often than not the introduction of SST operates in tandem with a reduction in staffing. When SST fails (as has been seen multiple times in the case of egates) the necessary staff to replace the service the SST now provide are not available.</p>	<p>To reduce the risk of chokepoints:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a robust system, that is not prone failure. • Assess the risks and costs associated with over reliance on SST, as this may create a vulnerability in the business case. • Regularly maintain the SST as per the provider instructions to minimise the risk of system break downs. • Schedule mandatory maintenance work during off-peak times to reduce the volume of customers impacted.
<p>9 Right to information.</p>	<p>To reduce risks to right to information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide supporting information and signage on the SST. • Outline and make accessible the terms & conditions of use/confidentiality. • Use legible and easy to understand terms. • Provide details of the data processing purposes. • Provide point of contact details for the data controller and processor. • Provide point of contact details for confidentiality issues. • Provide details on any access to/communication of identifiers to third parties. • Provide details on plans to use information to improve system performance. • Use default 'opt-out' function for any non/mandated processing. • Present the user's rights. • Provide information on the secure data storage method.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide information on any changes to data collected, purpose and confidentiality clauses.
10	Autonomy.	<p>To reduce risks to autonomy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement a design format that supports the decision-making power of the user, where allowed. • See also, risks related to dark patterns.
11	Balance of power.	<p>To ensure a balance of power:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement a design format that supports the decision-making power of the user, where allowed. • Ensure accountability of the operator. • Ensure the transparency of the data processing. • Provide easy access to alternative means to access the service for users unable to use the SST • Engage the user in the co-design and development of the SST to better reflect their needs and desires. • Understand the trade-off between design choices for different stakeholders (users, operators, providers) and justify the choices taken in relation to impacts on the user.
12	Service experience. Poor quality user experience can result in low adoption or uptake of a solution. This relates to not only the SST itself, but also the support provided to the user by supervising staff.	<p>To reduce risks to service experience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test the SST for human factors. • Provide a user-friendly interface. • Provide sufficient support staff to guide the user through the process. • Communicate any service disruptions promptly until normal service is restored.
13	Government/society relations. As SST are increasingly used in the management of digital identities, and by extension used to control access to (public) services. User experiences of SST are becoming a growing site of government/societal relations, whereby a breakdown in SST is viewed as a breakdown in the provision of the (public) service by the government. These issues are further complicated as SST often operate under public/private partnerships.	<p>To reduce risks to government/society relations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop robust systems capable of handling high volumes of demand. • Ensure the system is secure from attack and threats. • Implement fall back measures for when the system breaks down/fails. • Implement a communication plan to engage users for when the system breaks down/fails.

Table 7: ELSI Opportunities Self-Service Technologies

ELSI No.	Potential Opportunity	Suggested Actions to Enable/Enhance
1	Fraud detection. The introduction of SST can help to support a secure and robust identity management process.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robust solutions with improved capacity to detect MAD and APD attempts can help to deter fraud. • Robust solutions with strong security and privacy enhancing techniques can protect personal and sensitive personal data, reducing the risks of identity theft.
2	Bright patterns. SST that integrate bright patterns can provide users with great understanding of and control over their choices. This can help to promote societal values of fairness, transparency, and trust.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UI that encourages the choice and support fundamental rights of users. • The use of SST can provide the user with greater understanding of the process, providing an improved knowledge base to make informed choices. This requires the design and development of the SST to rely on high levels of transparency, accountability and bright patterns.
3	Increased convenience. The introduction of SST can help to speed up the service process, reducing queuing times, and provide the user with greater flexibility for when they complete the service task.	The use of SST can improve the convenience of consuming (public) services as it can reduce wait times, negate the need for appointments. Improvement to convenience should be validated against SMART KPIs.
4	Frees staff up to deal with more high-risk / sensitive tasks. The introduction of SST provides an opportunity to free up valuable human resources to focus on more complex/high risk cases of fraud.	The use of SST can help to refocus the deployment of human resources away from low risk/repetitive tasks. In addition to help manage increased workloads.
6	Supports seamless travel experience. The introduction of SST can help to reduce and/or remove potential points of friction in the travel journey.	The use of SST can help to speed up travel journeys and support the integration of multiple travel modalities (bus, rail, sea and air) across multiple actors and providers for seamless identity management.
7	Reduces risk of human bias/discrimination. The introduction of SST can help to reduce and/or remove human bias/discrimination, promoting societal values of fairness and equality.	The implementation of SST can support equal and fair treatment, providing bias has been removed from the technology development process.
8	Cost benefit. The introduction of SST can help to achieve a greater cost/benefit, while maintaining the same, if not an improved, level of service experience.	To determine the added value of SST a cost comparison of both current and planned business cases needs to be carried out. Cost should be measured not only in terms of financial cost but also compliance with ELSI, including but not

limited to user acceptance, data processing, reputation, risk of breakdown/failure, etc.

Any benefits derived from the introduction of SST should be passed along to the user to offset the costs of user labour.

4.1.4 From Component Level to Application Level

The risks and opportunities for biometric technologies, AI algorithms and SST draws on state-of-the-art guidance in relation to these topics. Many of the risk mitigation actions are already being implemented across the design and development process, with particular emphasis on data processing and system security. This issue is not only being addressed within technical development, but is being actively discussed and requested by end-user partners.

Next steps as part of T2.1 will include monitoring for compliance with risk mitigation measures. This process will ensure that are risks are being addressed systematically across all aspects of the design.

T2.3 will then translate these recommendations for mitigating/enhancing actions into requirements. This will include a prioritisation process. Prioritisation of risks will be decided taking inspiration from value-based design methodologies.¹⁴⁸ A MoSCoW prioritisation scheme will be applied in collaboration with consortium partners (from a technical and end user perspective) and sense-checked with representatives of Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) and members of the travelling public. Prioritised risks will then be assessed in next iteration of the IA carried out under T2.1, forming a feedback loop between the identification and assessment of ELSI risks and opportunities, their translation into requirements, and their further assessment. This will help to focus the assessment on the risks of most importance to the work EINSTEIN is carrying out. Of particular importance here is understanding the relationship between potential ELSI impacts on individuals level values and societal level values and the trade-offs involved in accommodating the requirements of multiple stakeholders within the constraints of the digital identity management operating ecosystem.

The following sections outline the integration of the three technologies assessed at component level, the expected use case and the work that is currently being undertaken per Application. This is followed by a review of potential impacts at Application level.

4.2 Application level

This section provides an initial assessment of how biometric technologies, AI, and SST will be incorporated in the EINSTEIN Applications, this includes:

- Online id issuance,
- Mobile document and identity check,
- Document authentication,
- Pre-registration for border crossing,
- EES kiosk with advanced fraud detection,
- Fast track for enrolled travellers.

Applications 1-3, respectively, target law enforcement authorities and will be addressed under WP5 – Police checks and document issuance applications. Applications 4-6, respectively, target border management authorities and will be addressed under WP4 – Border checks' applications.¹⁴⁹ The integration and interaction of these technologies may result in new ELSI risks and opportunities and/or may exacerbate risks and opportunities identified at the component level. As many of the applications will undergo further development, this level of analysis will be

¹⁴⁸ See IEEE 7000-2021.

¹⁴⁹ These groupings of law enforcement authorities and border management authorities are loosely applied, as depending on the structure of the specific organisation they may be considered as one actor or two separate actors, with different powers, rights and responsibilities. In addition, Application 3 is specifically designed for immigration authorities, who again, depending on the organisational structure may be a part of the law enforcement body or may be a separate entity (e.g. many countries have been engaged in processes of civilianisation, where civilian staff increasingly carry out front line work such as border checks).

The EINSTEIN project is funded by the European Union (EU) under G.A. no. 101121280 and UKRI Funding Service under IFS reference 10093453. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect the views of the EU/Executive Agency or UKRI. Neither the EU nor the granting authority nor UKRI can be held responsible for them.

repeated in the next iteration of the IA. Initial ELSI risks and opportunities identified at the component level should be consulted during the development process for compliance at the Application level.

Each Application is assigned with a **PROVISIONAL** risk level as per the AIA. However, as development is ongoing, and guidelines on how to comply with the AI Act are still maturing, this assessment will be reviewed and updated across the iterations of the IA as required. Where Applications are between risk levels, the higher risk level will be chosen as both law enforcement and border management use cases have been identified as especially prone to risks.

Finally, while the design and development of the Application's technical functions may be intended for one purpose, it does not prevent their use in other ways. The impacts of these unintended uses must also be considered. In addition, some of the Application development relies on products that have already been developed in-house and/or are being sourced as already available commercial solutions. These materials will not undergo further research design and development. Inputs sourced through these two strategies will not have the same degree of design flexibility as the research work carried out under EINSTEIN. However, their role/impacts will be incorporated into the IA process.

4.2.1 Application 1 – Online ID Issuance

Application 1 will provide users with the ability to take and upload a 'selfie' as part of an online application to ID issuing authorities to re-new existing identity or travel credentials. Online ID Issuance brings together biometric technologies (for facial image capture and comparison), AI algorithms (for FIQA, MAD and PAD assessment) and SST, as the user must carry out part of the application process unsupervised using their own device.

The ELSI risks and opportunities previously identified for these components (see Section 4.1) should be borne in mind for the development of the Application.

Application 1 will draw on algorithms developed for MAD and PAD within the iMARS and D4FLY projects, which will be further developed in EINSTEIN as part of WP3. Under EINSTEIN the Application will develop the Biometric Assessment Service (BAS) and web application for online ID applications and issuance. Through developing and testing the Application will be matured to TRL 7.

Regulation governing data processing: **GDPR**

PROVISIONAL AIA risk rating: **High Risk**.

4.2.1.1 Expected Use Case

ID issuing authorities across the EU and the globe are in the process of digitalising their ID renewal processes. The Online ID Issuance Application will allow a user to submit their renewal application via a web application. As part of this process, the user is required to submit a 'selfie'. This 'selfie', along with any existing reference biometric data (e.g. from previous identity documents/applications) will be sent to the secure EINSTEIN Biometric Assessment Server (BAS) for fraud detection and quality control checks. Assessments will be performed using algorithms for MAD and PAD detection, in addition to facial image quality assessment (FIQA). The BAS will interface with the ID issuing authorities current operating processes to return the scores for MAD, PAD and FIQA, with supporting confidence levels per AI component. Confidence levels are determined using standard performance metrics for FIQA, MAD, and PAD. This information will support the operator in the identity management process. The Application will be limited to EU passport holders, only.

As part of the application process, the operator may choose to share the results of the face image assessment with the user allowing them to upload another photo. However, this must be done carefully to mitigate the risk of opening the system for manipulation. The results of the MAD and PAD score will not be shared for security reasons.

The design of the BAS adopts a modular approach, so that it may be extended to host additional algorithms in the future. This will:

- Support provider agnostic solution development, preventing vendor lock-in.
- Allow the functionality of the BAS to be extended to include additional assessment types.
- Allow the functionality of the BAS to be extended to include additional biometric data (e.g. fingerprints).

The Online ID Issuance will support ID issuing authorities by improving workflow and enhancing the detection of fraudulent applications.

4.2.1.2 Current focus of design and development work

Currently, design and development work is focused on the BAS and the user web application. The BAS will host the algorithms for FIQA, MAD, with the potential to add algorithms for PAD. The algorithms for MAD and PAD are being developed under WP3. The algorithm for FIQA will use the Open Source Facial Image Quality (OFIQ) developed by the BSI (the Federal Cyber Security Authority of Germany) and is compliant with ISO/IEC 29794-5.

In addition, the current round of development has focused on understanding the operator's needs. The PUC for Application 1 is the UK Home Office, and more specifically His Majesty's Passport Office (HMPO). The HMPO has emphasised the importance of ensuring system security, both during the testing phase and for eventual deployment. And the importance of the user's journey to ensure a high quality of service provision, supporting the uptake of online ID issuance, and to reduce the rate of incomplete applications.

Next steps will target integration testing of the different components to assess their functionality and performance levels, before proceeding to the Living Lab testing scheduled for M12/M13.

4.2.2 Application 2 – Mobile Document and Identity Checks

Application 2 will provide law enforcement authorities with the capacity to perform mobile document and identity checks. This application will perform two kinds of authentication: 1) if the document itself is legitimate and 2) if document does indeed belong to the person in possession of it. Mobile Document and Identity Checks brings together biometric technologies (for facial image capture and comparison), and AI algorithms (for face verification, MAD and PAD assessment, and document authentication). As the Application will be operated solely by law enforcement authorities, it is not considered to be a SST.

The ELSI risks and opportunities previously identified for these components (see Section 4.1) should be borne in mind for the development of the Application.

Application 2 will draw on algorithms developed for MAD and PAD under the iMARS and D4FLY projects. It will also draw on document scanning and multispectral illumination developed under D4FLY. Under EINSTEIN, the Application will be extended to include document assessment in less controlled environments, with video processing. Through development and testing the Application will be matured to TRL 7.

Regulation governing data processing: **GDPR**

PROVISIONAL AIA risk rating: **High Risk**.

4.2.2.1 Expected Use Case

The authentication of ID documents plays an increasingly central role in the day-to-day work of border checks. Coupled with growing demands for solutions that provide the operator with greater flexibility to respond to physical and environmental constraints, the capability to perform mobile document and identity checks has been prioritised by law enforcement authorities. The Mobile Document and Identity Checks Application has two use cases:

- To support border checks (at the land border)
- To support on the spot document and identity checks in non-border contexts.

The Application will be available on a mobile, lightweight, smartphone solution. It will provide the operator with the capacity to scan a range of identity documents. This scan will be sent off device to a secure server, where it will be compared against a list of known document types to check for potential document fraud (focusing on MAD, PAD, and compliance with expected document security features). A document analysis module will also highlight suspicious areas of the travel document, if it is detected as not genuine, to aid operator detection of potential fraud modes. The results of the analysis will be returned to the operator's device. The Application will also support the operator to assess if the person who presented the document is the legitimate holder. Using the smartphone camera, the operator will take a live image capture of the traveller. An off-device comparison between the live photo and the photo from the document, with check for image manipulation using face morphing techniques. The results of the analysis will be returned to the operator's device with a recommendation on whether the reference photo is genuine or not. Operators will be provided with training on Application use, a manual and technical documentation pre-deployment. The Application's UI will also provide feedback to support technical use in the field (e.g. recommendations on how to capture images). Of particular importance here is mitigating any risk of profiling. This will be done through a combination of design features (logging and auditing) and training. This issue will be monitored across the development of the Application.

The Application will support the operator in performing border checks in addition to supporting on the spot document and identity checks in non-border contexts. These use cases raise different potential impacts as the ethical, legal, and societal expectations for identity management vary greatly between bordering and non-bordering contexts.

4.2.2.2 Focus of current design and development work

Current design and development work is focused on the modification of commercially available smartphones to accurately perform document information and image capture for travel documents, addressing issues of lighting and angles. The interplay of these issues in both document information and image capture can have serious impacts on the performance of the assessment, requiring detailed research and development work, especially in less controlled operating environments. The algorithms for MAD and PAD are being developed under WP3. The specific algorithm to support FIQA is still being discussed. The design of the Application will aim to:

- Achieve maximum offline functionality, to support use in remote areas/black spots.
- Adopt a 'plug 'n' play' approach, where the Application can be customised to operator needs.
- Be compatible with both Android and iOS devices, to avoid vendor lock in.

The PUC for Application 2 is the Greek border. As land BCP can vary greatly, understanding operational requirements has been highlighted as key. Next steps will target integration testing of the different components to assess their functionality and performance levels, before proceeding to the Living Lab testing scheduled for M12/M13.

4.2.3 Application 3 – Document Authentication

Application 3 will provide document experts with enhanced capabilities to authenticate identity, travel, and breeder documents. Document Authentication mainly focusses AI algorithms for printing technique recognition and analysis of biographic data; it may also operate on biometric data (fingerprint and facial image). As the Application will be operated solely by document experts, it is not considered to be an SST.

The ELSI risks and opportunities previously identified for these components (see Section 4.1) should be borne in mind for the development of the Application.

Application 3 will draw on document authentication capabilities developed under D4FLY. Under EINSTEIN, the Application will be extended to include new printing techniques recognition, incorporate privacy and security enhancing technologies, and develop hybrid tactical anomaly detection capabilities. The Application will be matured to TRL 7/8 through development and testing.

Regulation governing data processing: **GDPR**

PROVISIONAL AIA risk rating: **High Risk**.

4.2.3.1 Expected Use Case

The verification of travel documents is performed as part of the border check. Immigration authorities rely on document experts to verify the authenticity of both travel and breeder documents. Application 3 will integrate a series of algorithms to aid the authentication of documents by document experts. The algorithms will focus on the detection of potential MAD through the authentication of printing techniques; verify consistency and completeness; detect digital image tampering; confirm matching of stamps and signatures; and detect multiple detail types. The Application connects user groups across the work process using a distributed system. Document experts will have access to the Application via a central computer, whereas non-document experts (who are still required to assess documents) will be able to scan and upload documents to the Application via thin clients. The system performs a first line check on the document, with final authentication carried out by the operator. Adopting a hybrid approach, the operator can add annotated images and notes, based on expert knowledge, to complement the analysis performed by the Application. Documents marked as genuine by the Application will be checked using random sampling, to ensure the quality of the assessment and to check for potential false positives. Documents marked as fraudulent will be reviewed by an operator before further action is taken. Operators will be provided with training on Application use, in addition to a manual and technical documentation pre-deployment. The Application's UI will also provide feedback to support the user.

4.2.3.2 Focus of current design and development work

Current design and development is focused on developing the datasets required to develop and train the algorithms. As part of the development of the system, facial images will need to be processed, but as the system does not intend to carry out facial image comparison, the current design approach aims to either anonymise this region or replace this information with synthetic/publicly available facial image data. The design process places strong emphasis on the use of privacy enhancing technologies and techniques.

The PUC for Application 3 is with the Dutch Immigration Service (IND). Ongoing work has sought to better understand the use case and the current work processes for document authentication. As this Application will aim to achieve one of the highest TRLs in the project the maturation of its design and development will heavily influence its deployment.

Next steps will target integration testing of the different components to assess their functionality and performance levels, before proceeding to the Living Lab testing scheduled for M12/M13.

4.2.4 Application 4 – Pre-registration for border-crossing

Application 4 will allow travellers to pre-register personal data, biometric data, and border crossing information for verification before arrival at the border crossing point, providing access to a 'fast lane'. Pre-registration for border-crossing brings together biometric technologies (for facial image capture and comparison), AI algorithms (for FIQA, MAD and PAD assessment) and SST, as the traveller is expected to complete part of the identity management process prior to travel.

The ELSI risks and opportunities previously identified for these components (see Section 4.1) should be borne in mind for the development of the Application.

Application 4 will draw on previous research outputs developed under the SMILE project. Under EINSTEIN, the Application will be extended to integrate developments around Digital Travel Credentials (DTC) and eIDs. Through development and testing the Application will be matured to TRL 7.

Regulation governing data processing: **GDPR**

PROVISIONAL AIA risk rating: **High Risk**.

4.2.4.1 Expected Use Case

Border authorities are continually seeking to improve and economise the border crossing process, while maintaining high levels of confidence and accuracy in the security check. Innovative solutions to balance these requirements are increasingly important under a vision of seamless travel. The Application is expected to be operationalised across two business cases. 1) at the land border. And, 2) in conjunction with Application 6, at the sea and land (train) border. The first business case is described below, and the second business case is described under Application 6.

In advance of their journey, travellers will be able to access the Application via their smartphones or through a web portal, where they will remotely submit travel information, including:

- Time and date of travel
- Means of travel (e.g. car, bus)
- Expected BCP
- Biographic information
- Biometric information (facial image)

After this information is submitted, the user is provided with a unique ID number (uID). To create the uID, the photograph is processed and transformed into a biometric facial image template. This uID will be stored on a secure database and made available to the user for retrieval during the travel process. The uID will be protected through hashing (to produce a set of 64 alphanumeric characters, that can then be visualised as, for example, a QR code). The creation of the hash key provides a strong layer of security to the uID as reversal of the hash key to the original data is very difficult to do (it is both costly and time consuming). The creation of the uID establishes a trusted relationship between the traveller and their identity, removing the need to present their travel document (passport or passport card) for those with access to EU status. The user will be provided with access to service and support requests via the Application to help complete the submission of information.

The Application then forwards the information provided to the border authority in advance of travel. The information is checked prior to the traveller's arrival at the BCP, including MAD and PAD assessment. If no alerts are triggered, the user is provided with access to a fast lane to speed up the border crossing process. The uID is presented during the border crossing process, for confirmation, and a final ID check is performed, including biometric verification.

4.2.4.2 Focus of current design and development work

Currently development work is focused on capturing, reading and transferring data from the pre-registration application to the BCP. Future development of the Application is targeting availability to all traveller categories. The following functionalities are being focused on for the Living Lab testing:

- Restricted use case to EU only travellers for testing.
- Testing of the information capture, including passport scanning and face image capture.
- Testing of uID creation
- Testing of data transfer between the pre-registration Application and the biometric corridor (Application 6). Near Field Communication functionality still under discussion.
- Compatibility with android and iOS smartphones

Next steps will target integration testing of the different components to assess their functionality and performance levels, before proceeding to the Living Lab testing scheduled for M12/M13. With MAD and PAD assessment to be integrated in later prototypes.

4.2.5 Application 5 – EES kiosk with advance fraud detection

Application 5 will allow travellers subject to the EES to register personal data, biometric data, and border crossing information for verification in a semi-supervised environment at border crossing points using a dedicated kiosk. EES kiosk with advance fraud detection brings together biometric technologies (for facial image capture and verification, for fingerprint capture and identification, biometrics in video surveillance), AI algorithms (for FIQA, MAD and PAD assessment) and SST, as the traveller is expected to complete part of the identity management process themselves.

The ELSI risks and opportunities previously identified for these components (see Section 4.1) should be borne in mind for the development of the Application.

Application 5 will draw on previous research outputs developed under the FastPass project and internal development work at IDEMIA. Under EINSTEIN, the Application will be extended to include the integration of MAD and PAD, and anomaly detection using video surveillance. Through development and testing the Application will be matured to TRL 7.

Regulation governing data processing: **GDPR**

PROVISIONAL AIA risk rating: **High Risk**.

4.2.5.1 Expected Use Case

Under EES regulation, the introduction of SST is formalised as part of the border check process, enabling travellers to enrol biographical and biometric details in kiosks in a semi-supervised environment. Application 5 will focus on the integration of video analytics to support potential fraud detection during the enrolment and authentication of biometric and bibliographic data at EES kiosks. The use of SST must provide for adequate staffing to oversee the use of the kiosks. To support border authorities, additional remote monitoring of enrolment will be performed by video analytics. Algorithms will target the identification of unsuitable behaviours, e.g. multiple persons attempting to enrol simultaneously. In addition, algorithms for improved robustness of passport authentication will be integrated. The kiosk will also support document authentication. Application 5 will target third country nationals (TCNs), in particular travellers required to undergo checks as part of the Entry Exit System (EES).

4.2.5.2 Current focus of design and development work

The first round of development has focused on engaging with end user partners to understand and classify scenarios where potentially abnormal behaviours could be detected. Technical Application development will then work to determine how best to identify and distinguish them from non-fraudulent behaviours using the functionalities of the kiosk, video surveillance, and remote video analytics for MAD and PAD, in addition to biometric verification as per the EES requirements.

Next steps will leverage the integration of on-the-shelf components to test during the Living Lab, before combining the PAD algorithm (developed in WP3) with the CCTV stream to detect and counter fraudulent PAD patterns in further rounds of development.

4.2.6 Application 6 – Fast track for enrolled travellers

Application 6 will support travellers to seamlessly cross the border, using a corridor to capture and authenticate face and iris biometrics on the move. The corridor is supported by Application 4, pre-registration for border crossing. Fast track for enrolled travellers brings together biometric technologies (for facial image capture and identification, for iris capture and identification), AI algorithms (for FIQA, MAD and PAD assessment) and SST, as the traveller is expected to complete part of the identity management process themselves.

The ELSI risks and opportunities previously identified for these components (see Section 4.1) should be borne in mind for the development of the Application.

Application 6 will draw on previous research outputs developed under the D4FLY project. Under EINSTEIN, the Application will be extended to improve accessibility to different user groups. Through development and testing the Application will be matured to TRL 7.

Regulation governing data processing: **GDPR**

PROVISIONAL AIA risk rating: **High Risk**.

4.2.6.1 Expected Use Case

Under a vision of seamless travel, there are ongoing efforts to improve the experience of border crossings for bona fide travellers. This involves identifying and removing potential points of friction across the travellers' journey. One area that has been highlighted for improvement is the security check. Using the pre-registration app (Application 4), Application 6 provides users access to a contactless biometric corridor to cross sea and land (train) borders without stopping.¹⁵⁰ The traveller enters the corridor independently, initiating the corridor verification process by an interaction between the traveller's smartphone and the corridor's Near Field Communication (NFC) interface. The border crossing is supervised by an operator. In cases of a successful verification the traveller guidance system leads the traveller automatically to the exit of the corridor area without any direct interaction with a border guard. In cases of a negative verification result the traveller guidance system will lead the traveller to a border guard booth for further inspection. The corridor will use 'on-the-fly' biometric capture of face and iris to perform identity verification. This requires a high rate of frames/images captured per second and relies on intensive computational filtering to remove unusable images, to allow for a more accurate comparison. Travellers will be required to enrol face and iris biometric using a mobile kiosk before they enter the corridor. An enrolment station operated and supervised by a border guard must be used as the quality of image capture required for iris capture and comparison is not available on a smartphone, thus it cannot be performed in advance. Two types of scores will be produced:

- A matching score which compares points of comparison between the enrolled template and the live image capture. This requires that the quality assessment of images captured is performed live and the number of cameras used and the number of images captured will need to meet industry standards for face image quality. The scores for both face and iris verification will be sent to the biometric fusion module where the combined verification results score is calculated and displayed on the operator's device.
- A PAD detection score will also be produced for both face and iris, focusing on liveness detection.

After comparison the live image captures taken by the cameras in the corridor will be automatically deleted. The matching is carried out on the corridor and the scores are sent to the operators' device. As the Application relies on the processing of iris, there is no legal basis for mandatory participation by travellers. The business case for the

¹⁵⁰ Field tests will take place at sea and land borders during EINSTEIN. Post-project use cases are expected to also include air borders.

corridor is limited to voluntary travel schemes, such as frequent travellers' programmes or fast track programmes.¹⁵¹

4.2.6.2 Current focus of design and development work

Current design and development work has focused on the development of the corridor. This includes,

- Pillars for the capturing of the face and iris images on the move in the corridor, including 2D face capturing and matching, and automatic height adjustment for the iris capturing unit in the corridor.
- Basic design of the corridor that allows user guidance through the corridor and provides all basic functionalities defined in prototype 1.
- Local database for the storage of the UUID and the reference biometric templates for face and iris. This database is only a defined component for the first prototype to enable a first test. The best way for the biometric template storage considering GDPR, processes and integration into existing infrastructure is currently under discussion between WP4 partners, end-users and WP2 partners and will be a focus topic in the further phases of the project.
- Biometric fusion module. Whether a first version of the biometric fusion module will be available for the first prototype is currently under discussion. If the fusion module is not yet available for the first prototype a mock-up to represent this functionality will be used.
- NFC interface for mobile device to local corridor database communication
- Biometric Corridor Component Manager. This will use the general IT architecture envisioned for the final version and will cover components that are available in the first prototype
- Border Guard monitoring application. The application will display basic traveller information, the combined matching score (coming from the mock-up) and a red or green flag depending on the results. Which basic traveller information (e.g., face image or name) is displayed in the monitoring application of the first prototype is still under discussion. The presentation of the scoring on the UI of the operators' device is critical. This issue was highlighted during the D4FLY project and is being actively discussed within the EINSTEIN consortium. The current status of development has not addressed this issue yet, but options for different forms of presenting the information (e.g. flagging, numerical scores, traffic light system) and how to support the explainability of the fused scores, are being discussed.
- Privacy by-design and privacy-by default, in addition to a security-by design approaches are being fed into the development process.
- The automatic deletion of biometric templates processed as part of the verification process is a programmed trigger. The design of this is currently under discussion, but will be compliant with GDPR requirements.

4.2.7 Assessment of Potential Impacts Application 1 – 6

In addition to complying with the relevant Component level risks and opportunities identified under Section 4.1, the following impacts have been identified for the Applications at this stage of development.

¹⁵¹ The programmes described under this business case differ from National Facilitation Programmes legislated for under the EES regulation (for further details on National Facilitation Programmes under the EES, see: https://travel-europe.europa.eu/ees/national-facilitation-programmes_en). These programmes require a thorough check of travellers, which the Application does not have the capacity to support as it does not perform fingerprint checks against the VIS, as required for non-EU travellers or process fingerprint data for non-visa travellers accessing the EES.

4.2.7.1 Data Processing

For all applications the processing of personal data must be compliant with GDPR/LED.

Application 1: Online ID issuance will require the processing of both personal and biometric data. It will also subject these data to additional forms of processing by algorithmic means, through the inclusion of MAD, PAD, and FIQA algorithms. The operationalisation of the Application and their impacts on the process of issuing IDs must be considered in light of the principles of **legality, necessity** and **proportionality**.

Application 2: Mobile Document and Identity Checks will require the processing of both personal and biometric data. This includes facial images, with the potential to access fingerprints depending on the document type being assessed and the rights of the document holder (e.g. EU versus non-EU, International Protection applicants). As part of the document and identity check, the Application will develop a video streaming capability. As this functionality is still in development, its technical functionality is unclear. However, the use of videoing could result in covert surveillance and biometric capture. This issue will need to be assessed for ELSI. The off-device analysis performed by the Application will likely be completed using a local law enforcement system. Should the Application flag a potentially fraudulent document or identity, the operator may be able to request to check the document and identity details against other (large-scale) IT systems, (e.g. SIS II, VIS, EURODAC, SLTD). This would move the Application from verification matching (1:1) to authentication matching (1:N). The use case demands and expectations around interoperability with other IT systems have not yet been defined, and will need to be assessed for ELSI. Application 2 will implement SSI to enhancing privacy. The operationalisation of the Application and their impacts on the process of mobile document and identity checks must be considered in light of the principles of **legality, necessity** and **proportionality**.

Application 3: Document Authentication will require the processing of both personal and biometric data.¹⁵² The Application aim to speed up the processing time of document authentication, thereby resulting in a great quantity of personal data being processed. The Application will also not process additional personal data (e.g. names, marital status) as part of the working process. Application 3 will use federated learning to enhance privacy. The operationalisation of the Application and their impacts on the process of document authentication must be considered in light of the principles of **legality, necessity** and **proportionality**.

Application 4: Pre-registration for border-crossing will require the processing of both personal and biometric data. It will also subject these data to additional forms of processing by algorithmic means, through the inclusion of MAD and PAD algorithms. Application 4 will implement SSI to enhance privacy. And Blockchain will be used to produce an EBSI compliant wallet. The operationalisation of the Application and their impacts on the process of border crossing must be considered in light of the principles of **legality, necessity** and **proportionality**.

Application 5: EES kiosk for advance fraud detection will require the processing of both personal and biometric data. It will also subject these data to additional forms of processing by algorithmic means, through the inclusion of MAD and PAD algorithms. The legal basis for data processing is established in the EES regulation. However, the use of video surveillance raises additional risks. The Application does not intend to capture and process biometric data using the video surveillance in order to perform biometric recognition, however the potential impacts for retrospective remote biometric identification (RBI) must be considered as the Application develops. The technical details of the Application's use case have yet to be fully determined, but will need to be assessed for ELSI, this includes understanding:

- What (biometric) data is being capture by the video surveillance and how the relationship between the data processed and the detection of fraudulent behaviour determined? The science of abnormal behaviour

¹⁵² The aim of the Application is not to capture and process biometric data for identification purposes, but rather to ensure the authenticity of the document. However as both facial images and fingerprints will be processed as part of the authentication process, the system creates the conditions to *allow* for the unique identification of a natural person (as per the GDPR and LED definitions of biometric data), and have been included in the analysis.

detection is highly contested, and any claims must be well grounded in scientific evidence, with clear boundary conditions established and communicated to the operator.

- How the video surveillance data will be processed (including storage, deletions and accessible to which parties) how will the analysis integrate into the user's experience (UX).
- How the data processed within the kiosk with achieve interoperability with the EINSTEIN BAS and EU large-scale IT systems.

The operationalisation of the Application and their impacts on the process of implementing the EES and detecting potential fraud must be considered in light of the principles of **legality, necessity** and **proportionality** .

Application 6: Fast track for enrolled travellers will require the processing of both personal and biometric data. It will also subject these data to additional forms of processing by algorithmic means, through the inclusion of MAD and PAD algorithms. There is currently no legislative basis requiring the processing of iris as part of a border check. Rather the data must be provided on voluntary basis, and processed under 1 of the legal bases identified under the GDPR (See Chapter 3). The optimal management of biometric data (sensitive personal data) between the enrolment kiosk and the corridor is being reviewed. This process needs to balance the requirements of security, fundamental rights, accessibility to various traveller groups, and support the seamless travel process. Two options are currently under discussion:

Option A. The creation of a local database in which the biometric templates captured during enrolment are stored and automatically accessed via the corridor (by a secure internal connection) for comparison with the live images captured as the user moves through the corridor. This requires that the biometric templates are stored so they can be accessed each time the travellers cross the border. This database would have to be reproduced for each country and travellers would have to enrol and store their data for each country.

Option B. The biometric template is created on the kiosk and sent back to the smartphone of the travellers. The biometric template is stored on the smartphone of the traveller and sent to the corridor each time the users wishes to travel. This data would need to be sent by public wi-fi. The amount of data to be transferred is significant and would add additional time to the processing.

For the purposes of the living lab testing, Option A has been selected. This design choice has been made to allow the testing of the functionality of the image capture and assessment to proceed. However, it does not cause a dependency on the database and this issue still remains open at a design level for further assessment. This assessment will need to consider future proofing for SSI and the trade-off between the promise of convenience/speed (for the cost of voluntarily submitting additional biometrics) and the average processing times expected under options A and B above. The EDPS has recently adopted an opinion on the use of facial recognition to streamline airport passenger flows.¹⁵³ The opinion review 4 scenarios for compliance with Articles 5 (1)(e) and (f), 25 and 32 of the GDPR. Scenarios 1 and 2 were deemed compliant, provided the necessary safeguards and protections were put in place. Scenarios 3 and 4 were deemed non-complaint. Scenarios 1 and 2 map onto Options B and A, respectively.

- Scenario 1: storage of enrolled biometric template only in the hands of the individual, for authentication.
- Scenario 2: centralised storage of enrolled biometric template in an encrypted form within the airport and with a key/secret solely in the passenger's hands, for authentication.
- Scenario 3: centralised storage in a database within the airport, under the control of the airport operator.
- Scenario 4: centralised storage in a cloud, under the control of the airline company.

Both scenarios 1 and 2 are limited to verification (1:1 matching) and do not address the business case requirements for thorough checks. The operationalisation of the Application and the impacts on the process of border crossing must be considered in light of the principles of **legality, necessity** and **proportionality**.

¹⁵³ EDPS, Opinion 11/2024.

4.2.7.2 System security

Each of the Applications must be designed to be secure, with a particular focus on the security of data processing. The Applications must address the risks and threats of incorporating SST and remote technologies into the identity management process, both to the individual and to society at large.

4.2.7.3 Digitalisation

Each of the Applications support the digitalisation of their use case, either by providing operator led technologies or self-service technologies. Impacts relating to digitalisation for the Applications are outlined below.

The Applications can have a potentially negative impact on privacy as the use cases process both personal data and special personal category data using high-risk technologies (biometrics and AI systems) in high-risk contexts (border management and law enforcement) in an ecosystem of interoperability. The processing of multiple pieces of personal data across multiple systems increases the risk of profiling. The Applications can also have a positive impact on privacy, as embedding PET in the design can set the standard for future deployment and use.

The Applications can have a potentially negative impact on safety and security, as the development of the Application places personal and special category personal data at risk to security breaches and vulnerabilities. The Applications can also a positive impact on safety and security, as the aim of the Application is to detect and prevent fraud.

The Applications can have a negative impact on balance of power as there is limited transparency to the algorithmic assessment process and potentially reduced capacity of the user to challenge the decision-making process. However, the Applications can have a positive impact on balance of power through agnostic vendor design, and through the use of privacy enhancing techniques, so long as the user is empowered to make informed choices.

The Applications incorporating SST can have a negative impact on autonomy as user may feel restrained by their digital literacy and the format of the UI. Designers must address the risk of dark patterns. This impacts on the autonomy of the user, as it incorporates novel technologies that the user may not be familiar with. Therefore, information has to be provided in a convenient, easy to identify and understandable way. However, many border crossing points struggle with limited available space which reduces the physical options to display the necessary information to the traveller. Future co-design and development work will need to address this requirement. The Applications incorporating SST can have a positive impact on autonomy as users have greater control over the service encounter and experience.

The Applications that are operator-led can have a negative impact on autonomy as the operator may feel restrained to follow the results of the Application even if they are contrary to their own assessment. The Application UI may also restrict the autonomy of the operator. Additionally, the risk of automation bias must be addressed through proper training. The Applications that are operator-led can have a positive impact on autonomy as the Applications may support the operator to feel empowered in their decision-making.

The Applications incorporating SST can have a negative impact on human dignity as limitations in digital literacy and digital divides may prevent certain user groups from availing of the service. How best to achieve equitable access to the service must be considered, as (in)accessibility (physically, financially, and socially) can further exacerbate inequalities. The Applications can have a negative impact on human dignity as a lack of access to human support staff to guide the user when they encounter challenges can result in feelings of frustration. The risk of over relying on the digital literacy and skills of the user must be considered, and alternative forms of service provision must be made available. The Applications incorporating SST can have a positive impact on human dignity as they reduce the risk of human bias and discrimination.

The Applications that are operator-led can have a negative impact on human dignity as the Applications may minimise the capacity of the operator to frame the assessment in terms of social relations, and moral and ethical obligation, resulting in increased risk of dehumanisation. There is a further risk of dehumanisation as the use of the

Applications can intersect with cultural and social acceptance of identity management. There is also a risk of deskilling, which must be considered in light of the opportunities for upskilling and the provision of expanded capabilities for operators.

The Applications can have a negative impact on a sense of justice as poor Application development may result in unacceptable levels of bias leading to potential discrimination, and exclusion. The Applications can have a positive impact on a sense of justice as they help to detect and prevent fraud.

Finally, factors relating to the ethical, legal, and social acceptance of Applications that integrate both biometric, AI, and SST (with the exception of Applications 2 and 3) must also be considered in relation to how the public frames and assesses the potential impacts of the Applications.

4.2.7.4 Consequences of the scoring

Each of the Applications incorporates algorithms that will produce scores for FIQA, MAD, and PAD. The impacts of receiving a low score must be considered:

- Does a low score results in impacts to future identity uses?
- Does a low score results in categorisation to a risk profile?
- Does a low score trigger an investigative response into potential fraud?
- What capacity does a user have to challenge the results of the score and how can this challenge be evidenced to a satisfactory level that the score is adjusted/deleted?
- Can the system differentiate between fraudulent and non-fraudulent causes of a low score? Is the significance of this overlap well understood?

The impacts of the scoring are serious and far reaching as they may interfere with fundamental rights (e.g. the right to respect for private and family life, protection of personal data, the right to freedom of movement, and prohibition of discrimination). Central to this is the explainability of the scores produced by the Application. The scores is not intended to function in a decision-making capacity, but should support the (supervising) operator's assessment. The role of the score must be clearly communicated through training. The boundary conditions which can impact the performance of the score must be well understood and clearly communicated to the (supervising) operator. Given the increasing trend of criminalising migration, the differentiation between a low score due to technical limitations and a low score due to fraud must be clearly established.

4.2.7.5 AI Act Compliance

Given the potential impacts of the Applications, and their context of operation, the Applications have been provisionally assessed as high risk, under the current AI Act classification scheme. As the Applications and their use cases mature, the potential impacts will be further assessed. Of particular importance here is human oversight, proper training, and logging.

These issues, and any others that emerge as the Applications mature, will be closely monitored across the project. Future iterations of the IA will include an analysis of the EINSTEIN solutions from an ecosystem/interoperability perspective. This level of analysis looks at the wider operating environment in which the Application will be deployed.

5 Conclusions

The embedding of the initial IA results will be crucial to ensure the recommendations are actively incorporated in the development of the EINSTEIN applications. The translation of the ELSI recommendations into a requirement format (T2.3, see below for further details) will be complemented by a requirements traceability matrix. The engagement work of T2.1 with work packages 3-5 will continue, and expand to include WP6 on piloting and WP7 on exploitation.

T2.1 is not a stand alone task, but rather integrates with the ongoing work of the other tasks of the WP2. The following section outlines how the results of this initial impact assessment will be used in the other tasks of WP2, in addition to next steps describing planned activities to support the second iteration of the impact assessment.

The findings of T2.1 and T2.2 will guide the work of T2.3, focusing on the translation of ELSI recommendations into functional and non-functional requirements. This process will align with the work and methodology of T2.4, where the technical requirements of the applications are being prepared. As part of the technical requirements development T2.4 will engage end-users and technical development partner to develop user stories. The development of the user stories will provide an opportunity to identify where ELSI sits in the workflows and processes of end-users, focusing on areas of mutual support and any potential points of friction or contradiction. For example, initial conversations with end-user partners show that they are actively monitoring their current systems for compliance with data processing, flagging potential sources of bias/discrimination, and are heavily invested in understanding the user experience. This process will be implemented around value-based design methods (IEEE 7000 – 2021).

Engagement with end-user partners will be crucial to better understanding both their needs, and the operational constraints that shape their ability to deploy the solutions in line with an ELSI perspective. Particular attention will be paid to compliance with the AI Act.

The next round of IA will focus on the Application level, as the solutions mature in their functionalities and increase in complexity vis-à-vis the integration of components. The component level analysis will be reviewed and updated as required, in particular the guidance on AI algorithms as the outputs of WP3 mature, to ensure the recommendations provided here have been incorporated in the design process.

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Annexes

ANNEX 1: High-risk systems according to the AI Act

Annex III of the AI Act (Council of the EU and European Parliament, 2024c, p.424).

High-risk AI systems pursuant to Article 6(2) are the AI systems listed in any of the following areas:

1. Biometrics, in so far as their use is permitted under relevant Union or national law:

(a) **remote biometric identification systems.**

This shall **not** include AI systems **intended to be used for biometric verification the sole purpose of which is to confirm that a specific natural person is the person he or she claims to be;**

(b) AI systems intended to be used for **biometric categorisation**, according to sensitive or protected attributes or characteristics based on the inference of those attributes or characteristics;

(c) AI systems intended to be used for emotion recognition.

2. Critical infrastructure:

(a) AI systems intended to be used as safety components in the management and operation of critical digital infrastructure, road traffic, or in the supply of water, gas, heating or electricity.

3. Education and vocational training:

(a) AI systems intended to be used to determine access or admission or to assign natural persons to educational and vocational training institutions at all levels;

(b) AI systems intended to be used to evaluate learning outcomes, including when those outcomes are used to steer the learning process of natural persons in educational and vocational training institutions at all levels;

(c) AI systems intended to be used for the purpose of assessing the appropriate level of education that an individual will receive or will be able to access, in the context of or within educational and vocational training institutions at all levels;

(d) AI systems intended to be used for monitoring and detecting prohibited behaviour of students during tests in the context of or within educational and vocational training institutions at all levels.

4. Employment, workers management and access to self-employment:

(a) AI systems intended to be used for the recruitment or selection of natural persons, in particular to place targeted job advertisements, to analyse and filter job applications, and to evaluate candidates;

(b) AI systems intended to be used to make decisions affecting terms of work-related relationships, the promotion or termination of work-related contractual relationships, to allocate tasks based on individual behaviour or personal traits or characteristics or to monitor and evaluate the performance and behaviour of persons in such relationships.

5. Access to and enjoyment of essential private services and essential public services and benefits:

(a) AI systems intended to be used by public authorities or on behalf of public authorities to evaluate the eligibility of natural persons for essential public assistance benefits and services, including healthcare services, as well as to grant, reduce, revoke, or reclaim such benefits and services;

(b) AI systems intended to be used to evaluate the creditworthiness of natural persons or establish their credit score, with the exception of AI systems used for the purpose of detecting financial fraud;

(c) AI systems intended to be used for risk assessment and pricing in relation to natural persons in the case of life and health insurance;

(d) AI systems intended to evaluate and classify emergency calls by natural persons or to be used to dispatch, or to establish priority in the dispatching of, emergency first response services, including by police, firefighters and medical aid, as well as of emergency healthcare patient triage systems.

6. Law enforcement, in so far as their use is permitted under relevant Union or national law:

(a) AI systems **intended to be used by or on behalf of law enforcement authorities**, or by Union institutions, bodies, offices or agencies **in support of law enforcement authorities or on their behalf to assess the risk of a natural person becoming the victim of criminal offences**;

(b) AI systems intended to be used by or on behalf of law enforcement authorities or by Union institutions, bodies, offices or agencies in support of law enforcement authorities as polygraphs or similar tools;

(c) AI systems intended to be used by or on behalf of law enforcement authorities, or by Union institutions, bodies, offices or agencies, in support of law enforcement authorities to evaluate the reliability of evidence in the course of the investigation or prosecution of criminal offences;

(d) AI systems intended to be used by law enforcement authorities or on their behalf or by Union institutions, bodies, offices or agencies in support of law enforcement authorities for assessing the risk of a natural person offending or re-offending not solely on the basis of the profiling of natural persons as referred to in Article 3(4) of Directive (EU) 2016/680, or to assess personality traits and characteristics or past criminal behaviour of natural persons or groups;

(e) AI systems intended to be used by or on behalf of law enforcement authorities or by Union institutions, bodies, offices or agencies in support of law enforcement authorities **for the profiling of natural persons as referred to in Article 3(4) of Directive (EU) 2016/680 in the course of the detection, investigation or prosecution of criminal offences**.

7. Migration, asylum and border control management, in so far as their use is permitted under relevant Union or national law:

(a) AI systems intended to be used by or on behalf of competent public authorities or by Union institutions, bodies, offices or agencies as polygraphs or similar tools;

(b) AI systems **intended to be used by or on behalf of competent public authorities** or by Union institutions, bodies, offices or agencies **to assess a risk, including a security risk, a risk of irregular migration, or a health risk, posed by a natural person who intends to enter or who has entered into the territory of a Member State**;

(c) AI systems intended to be used by or on behalf of competent public authorities or by Union institutions, bodies, offices or agencies **to assist competent public authorities for the examination of applications for asylum, visa or residence permits and for associated complaints with regard to the eligibility of the natural persons applying for a status**, including related assessments of the reliability of evidence;

(d) AI systems intended to be used by or on behalf of competent public authorities, or by Union institutions, bodies, offices or agencies, **in the context of migration, asylum or border control management, for the purpose of detecting, recognising or identifying natural persons, with the exception of the verification of travel documents**.

8. Administration of justice and democratic processes:

(a) AI systems intended to be used by a judicial authority or on their behalf to assist a judicial authority in researching and interpreting facts and the law and in applying the law to a concrete set of facts, or to be used in a similar way in alternative dispute resolution;

(b) AI systems intended to be used for influencing the outcome of an election or referendum or the voting behaviour of natural persons in the exercise of their vote in elections or referenda. This does not include AI systems to the output of which natural persons are not directly exposed, such as tools used to organise, optimise or structure political campaigns from an administrative or logistical point of view.

ANNEX 2: Requirements for high-risk AI systems, as per the AI Act

Article 9: Risk management system

1. A risk management system shall be established, implemented, documented and maintained in relation to high-risk AI systems.

2. The risk management system shall be understood as a continuous iterative process planned and run throughout the entire lifecycle of a high-risk AI system, requiring regular systematic review and updating. It shall comprise the following steps:

(a) the identification and analysis of the known and the reasonably foreseeable risks that the high-risk AI system can pose to health, safety or fundamental rights when the high-risk AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose;

(b) the estimation and evaluation of the risks that may emerge when the high-risk AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose, and under conditions of reasonably foreseeable misuse;

(c) the evaluation of other risks possibly arising, based on the analysis of data gathered from the post-market monitoring system referred to in Article 72;

(d) the adoption of appropriate and targeted risk management measures designed to address the risks identified pursuant to point (a).

3. The risks referred to in this Article shall concern only those which may be reasonably mitigated or eliminated through the development or design of the high-risk AI system, or the provision of adequate technical information.

4. The risk management measures referred to in paragraph 2, point (d), shall give due consideration to the effects and possible interaction resulting from the combined application of the requirements set out in this Section, with a view to minimising risks more effectively while achieving an appropriate balance in implementing the measures to fulfil those requirements.

5. The risk management measures referred to in paragraph 2, point (d), shall be such that the relevant residual risk associated with each hazard, as well as the overall residual risk of the high-risk AI systems is judged to be acceptable.

In identifying the most appropriate risk management measures, the following shall be ensured:

(a) elimination or reduction of identified and evaluated risks pursuant to paragraph 2 as far as technically feasible through adequate design and development of the high-risk AI system;

(b) where appropriate, implementation of adequate mitigation and control measures addressing risks that cannot be eliminated;

(c) provision of information required pursuant to Article 13 and, where appropriate, training to deployers.

With a view to eliminating or reducing risks related to the use of the high-risk AI system, due consideration shall be given to the technical knowledge, experience, education, the training to be expected by the deployer, and the presumable context in which the system is intended to be used.

6. High-risk AI systems shall be tested for the purpose of identifying the most appropriate and targeted risk management measures. Testing shall ensure that high-risk AI systems perform consistently for their intended purpose and that they are in compliance with the requirements set out in this Section.

7. Testing procedures may include testing in real-world conditions in accordance with Article 60.

8. The testing of high-risk AI systems shall be performed, as appropriate, at any time throughout the development process, and, in any event, prior to their being placed on the market or put into service. Testing shall be carried out against prior defined metrics and probabilistic thresholds that are appropriate to the intended purpose of the high-risk AI system.

9. When implementing the risk management system as provided for in paragraphs 1 to 7, providers shall give consideration to whether in view of its intended purpose the high-risk AI system is likely to have an adverse impact on persons under the age of 18 and, as appropriate, other groups of vulnerable persons.

10. For providers of high-risk AI systems that are subject to requirements regarding internal risk management processes under other relevant provisions of Union law, the aspects provided in paragraphs 1 to 9 may be part of, or combined with, the risk management procedures established pursuant to that law.

Article 10: Data and data governance

1. High-risk AI systems which make use of techniques involving the training of AI models with data shall be developed on the basis of training, validation and testing data sets that meet the quality criteria referred to in paragraphs 2 to 5 whenever such data sets are used.

2. Training, validation and testing data sets shall be subject to data governance and management practices appropriate for the intended purpose of the high-risk AI system.

Those practices shall concern in particular:

- (a) the relevant design choices;
- (b) data collection processes and the origin of data, and in the case of personal data, the original purpose of the data collection;
- (c) relevant data-preparation processing operations, such as annotation, labelling, cleaning, updating, enrichment and aggregation;
- (d) the formulation of assumptions, in particular with respect to the information that the data are supposed to measure and represent;
- (e) an assessment of the availability, quantity and suitability of the data sets that are needed;
- (f) examination in view of possible biases that are likely to affect the health and safety of persons, have a negative impact on fundamental rights or lead to discrimination prohibited under Union law, especially where data outputs influence inputs for future operations;
- (g) appropriate measures to detect, prevent and mitigate possible biases identified according to point (f);
- (h) the identification of relevant data gaps or shortcomings that prevent compliance with this Regulation, and how those gaps and shortcomings can be addressed.

3. Training, validation and testing data sets shall be relevant, sufficiently representative, and to the best extent possible, free of errors and complete in view of the intended purpose. They shall have the appropriate statistical properties, including, where applicable, as regards the persons or groups of persons in relation to whom the high-risk AI system is intended to be used. Those characteristics of the data sets may be met at the level of individual data sets or at the level of a combination thereof.

4. Data sets shall take into account, to the extent required by the intended purpose, the characteristics or elements that are particular to the specific geographical, contextual, behavioural or functional setting within which the high-risk AI system is intended to be used.

5. To the extent that it is strictly necessary for the purpose of ensuring bias detection and correction in relation to the high-risk AI systems in accordance with paragraph (2), points (f) and (g) of this Article, the providers of such systems may exceptionally process special categories of personal data, subject to appropriate safeguards for the fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons. In addition to the provisions set out in Regulation (EU) 2016/679, Directive (EU) 2016/680 and Regulation (EU) 2018/1725, all the following conditions shall apply in order for such processing to occur:

- (a) the bias detection and correction cannot be effectively fulfilled by processing other data, including synthetic or anonymised data;

- (b) the special categories of personal data are subject to technical limitations on the re-use of the personal data, and state-of-the-art security and privacy-preserving measures, including pseudonymisation;
- (c) the special categories of personal data are subject to measures to ensure that the personal data processed are secured, protected, subject to suitable safeguards, including strict controls and documentation of the access, to avoid misuse and ensure that only authorised persons with appropriate confidentiality obligations have access to those personal data;
- (d) the personal data in the special categories of personal data are not to be transmitted, transferred or otherwise accessed by other parties;
- (e) the personal data in the special categories of personal data are deleted once the bias has been corrected or the personal data has reached the end of its retention period, whichever comes first;
- (f) the records of processing activities pursuant to Regulations (EU) 2016/679 and (EU) 2018/1725 and Directive (EU) 2016/680 include the reasons why the processing of special categories of personal data was strictly necessary to detect and correct biases, and why that objective could not be achieved by processing other data.

6. For the development of high-risk AI systems not using techniques involving the training of AI models, paragraphs 2 to 5 apply only to the testing data sets.

Article 11: Technical documentation

1. The technical documentation of a high-risk AI system shall be drawn up before that system is placed on the market or put into service and shall be kept up-to date.

The technical documentation shall be drawn up in such a way as to demonstrate that the high-risk AI system complies with the requirements set out in this Section and to provide national competent authorities and notified bodies with the necessary information in a clear and comprehensive form to assess the compliance of the AI system with those requirements. It shall contain, at a minimum, the elements set out in Annex IV. SMEs, including start-ups, may provide the elements of the technical documentation specified in Annex IV in a simplified manner. For this purpose, the Commission shall establish a simplified technical documentation form targeted at the needs of small and microenterprises. Where an SME, including a start-up, opts to provide the information required in Annex IV in a simplified manner, it shall use the form referred to in this paragraph. Notified bodies shall accept the form for the purposes of the conformity assessment.

2. Where a high-risk AI system related to a product covered by the Union harmonisation legislation listed in Section A of Annex I is placed on the market or put into service, a single set of technical documentation shall be drawn up containing all the information set out in paragraph 1, as well as the information required under those legal acts.

3. The Commission is empowered adopt delegated acts in accordance with Article 97 to amend Annex IV where necessary to ensure that, in the light of technical progress, the technical documentation provides all the information necessary to assess the compliance of the system with the requirements set out in this Section.

Article 12: Record-keeping

1. High-risk AI systems shall technically allow for the automatic recording of events ('logs') over their lifetime.
2. In order to ensure a level of traceability of the functioning of a high-risk AI system that is appropriate to the intended purpose of the system, logging capabilities shall enable the recording of events relevant for:
 - (a) identifying situations that may result in the high-risk AI system presenting a risk within the meaning of Article 79(1) or in a substantial modification;
 - (b) facilitating the post-market monitoring referred to in Article 72; and
 - (c) monitoring the operation of high-risk AI systems referred to in Article 26(6).

3. For high-risk AI systems referred to in point 1 (a) of Annex III, the logging capabilities shall provide, at a minimum:
- (a) recording of the period of each use of the system (start date and time and end date and time of each use);
 - (b) the reference database against which input data has been checked by the system;
 - (c) the input data for which the search has led to a match;
 - (d) the identification of the natural persons involved in the verification of the results, as referred to in Article 14(5).

Article 13: Transparency and provision of information to deployers

1. High-risk AI systems shall be designed and developed in such a way as to ensure that their operation is sufficiently transparent to enable deployers to interpret a system's output and use it appropriately. An appropriate type and degree of transparency shall be ensured with a view to achieving compliance with the relevant obligations of the provider and deployer set out in Section 3.
2. High-risk AI systems shall be accompanied by instructions for use in an appropriate digital format or otherwise that include concise, complete, correct and clear information that is relevant, accessible and comprehensible to deployers.
3. The instructions for use shall contain at least the following information:
- (a) the identity and the contact details of the provider and, where applicable, of its authorised representative;
 - (b) the characteristics, capabilities and limitations of performance of the high-risk AI system, including:
 - (i) its intended purpose;
 - (ii) the level of accuracy, including its metrics, robustness and cybersecurity referred to in Article 15 against which the high-risk AI system has been tested and validated and which can be expected, and any known and foreseeable circumstances that may have an impact on that expected level of accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity;
 - (iii) any known or foreseeable circumstance, related to the use of the high-risk AI system in accordance with its intended purpose or under conditions of reasonably foreseeable misuse, which may lead to risks to the health and safety or fundamental rights referred to in Article 9(2);
 - (iv) where applicable, the technical capabilities and characteristics of the high-risk AI system to provide information that is relevant to explain its output;
 - (v) when appropriate, its performance regarding specific persons or groups of persons on which the system is intended to be used;
 - (vi) when appropriate, specifications for the input data, or any other relevant information in terms of the training, validation and testing data sets used, taking into account the intended purpose of the high-risk AI system;
 - (vii) where applicable, information to enable deployers to interpret the output of the high-risk AI system and use it appropriately;
 - (c) the changes to the high-risk AI system and its performance which have been predetermined by the provider at the moment of the initial conformity assessment, if any;
 - (d) the human oversight measures referred to in Article 14, including the technical measures put in place to facilitate the interpretation of the outputs of the high-risk AI systems by the deployers;

- (e) the computational and hardware resources needed, the expected lifetime of the high-risk AI system and any necessary maintenance and care measures, including their frequency, to ensure the proper functioning of that AI system, including as regards software updates;
- (f) where relevant, a description of the mechanisms included within the high-risk AI system that allows deployers to properly collect, store and interpret the logs in accordance with Article 12.

Article 14: Human oversight

1. High-risk AI systems shall be designed and developed in such a way, including with appropriate human-machine interface tools, that they can be effectively overseen by natural persons during the period in which they are in use.
2. Human oversight shall aim to prevent or minimise the risks to health, safety or fundamental rights that may emerge when a high-risk AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose or under conditions of reasonably foreseeable misuse, in particular where such risks persist despite the application of other requirements set out in this Section.
3. The oversight measures shall be commensurate to the risks, level of autonomy and context of use of the high-risk AI system, and shall be ensured through either one or both of the following types of measures:
 - (a) measures identified and built, when technically feasible, into the high-risk AI system by the provider before it is placed on the market or put into service;
 - (b) measures identified by the provider before placing the high-risk AI system on the market or putting it into service and that are appropriate to be implemented by the deployer.
4. For the purpose of implementing paragraphs 1, 2 and 3, the high-risk AI system shall be provided to the user in such a way that natural persons to whom human oversight is assigned are enabled, as appropriate and proportionate to the following circumstances:
 - (a) to properly understand the relevant capacities and limitations of the high-risk AI system and be able to duly monitor its operation, including in view of detecting and addressing anomalies, dysfunctions and unexpected performance;
 - (b) to remain aware of the possible tendency of automatically relying or over-relying on the output produced by a high-risk AI system (automation bias), in particular for high-risk AI systems used to provide information or recommendations for decisions to be taken by natural persons;
 - (c) to correctly interpret the high-risk AI system's output, taking into account, for example, the interpretation tools and methods available;
 - (d) to decide, in any particular situation, not to use the high-risk AI system or to otherwise disregard, override or reverse the output of the high-risk AI system;
 - (e) to intervene in the operation of the high-risk AI system or interrupt the system through a 'stop' button or a similar procedure that allows the system to come to a halt in a safe state.
5. For high-risk AI systems referred to in point 1(a) of Annex III, the measures referred to in paragraph 3 of this Article shall be such as to ensure that, in addition, no action or decision is taken by the deployer on the basis of the identification resulting from the system unless that identification has been separately verified and confirmed by at least two natural persons with the necessary competence, training and authority.

The requirement for a separate verification by at least two natural persons shall not apply to high-risk AI systems used for the purposes of law enforcement, migration, border control or asylum, where Union or national law considers the application of this requirement to be disproportionate.

Article 15: Accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity

1. High-risk AI systems shall be designed and developed in such a way that they achieve an appropriate level of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity, and that they perform consistently in those respects throughout their lifecycle.

2. To address the technical aspects of how to measure the appropriate levels of accuracy and robustness set out in paragraph 1 and any other relevant performance metrics, the Commission shall, in cooperation with relevant stakeholder and organisations such as metrology and benchmarking authorities, encourage, as appropriate, the development of benchmarks and measurement methodologies.

3. The levels of accuracy and the relevant accuracy metrics of high-risk AI systems shall be declared in the accompanying instructions of use.

4. High-risk AI systems shall be as resilient as possible regarding errors, faults or inconsistencies that may occur within the system or the environment in which the system operates, in particular due to their interaction with natural persons or other systems. Technical and organisational measures shall be taken towards this regard.

The robustness of high-risk AI systems may be achieved through technical redundancy solutions, which may include backup or fail-safe plans.

High-risk AI systems that continue to learn after being placed on the market or put into service shall be developed in such a way as to eliminate or reduce as far as possible the risk of possibly biased outputs influencing input for future operations ('feedback loops'), and as to ensure that any such feedback loops are duly addressed with appropriate mitigation measures.

5. High-risk AI systems shall be resilient against attempts by unauthorised third parties to alter their use, outputs or performance by exploiting system vulnerabilities.

The technical solutions aiming to ensure the cybersecurity of high-risk AI systems shall be appropriate to the relevant circumstances and the risks.

The technical solutions to address AI specific vulnerabilities shall include, where appropriate, measures to prevent, detect, respond to, resolve and control for attacks trying to manipulate the training data set ('data poisoning'), or pre-trained components used in training ('model poisoning'), inputs designed to cause the AI model to make a mistake ('adversarial examples' or 'model evasion'), confidentiality attacks.

ANNEX 3: ENISA good practices for Remote ID proofing

- Environmental controls
 - Proper lighting conditions
 - Definition of minimum multimedia specifications
 - RIDP application client side architecture
- Technical controls – PAD
 - Hardware based controls
 - Software based controls
 - Static
 - Dynamic
 - 3D-geometry based
 - Phoneme-viseme mismatch detection
 - Light absorption-reflection analysis
 - Combined PAD methods
- Technical Controls – IAD
 - Camera anti-tampering
 - Deterrent software controls

- Session metadata analysis
- Automated artefact detection
- Identity document controls
 - Combined PAD and IAD methods
 - Liveness checks
 - Visual security features verification
 - OCR data extraction
 - MRZ verification
 - NFC screening
 - Modern document security features
 - Multimodal biometric verification
- Procedural controls
 - Challenge-response mechanisms
 - Multimodal biometric verification
 - Human operator-based verification
 - Using trusted identification sources
 - Document status look up
 - List of permitted document types
 - Stricter requirement for the biometric NFC chip photo
 - Threat monitoring
- Organisational controls
 - Identity fraud-oriented risk assessment and treatment
 - Alignment and adherence to recognised standards
 - Use of tested software products and components
 - Mandatory and recurring penetration tests, supplementary spoof bounty programmes

